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Hospital Acquired Infections in a Selected Tertiary Level Hospital of Rangpur City

MH Zaman¹, S Ferdouse²

Abstract

Objectives: To find out the proportion, to determine the average length of stay at hospital and to estimate the cost of treatment for hospital-acquired infections in a tertiary level hospital of Rangpur City.

Materials and Methods: This descriptive type of cross sectional study was conducted on purposively selected 200 admitted patients in a tertiary level hospital. Among them 100 were HAI patients and 100 were non HAI. Data were collected through duly pretested interviewer administered questionnaire and observation checklist.

Place and period of study: This study was conducted in Rangpur Medical College Hospital (RpMCH), Rangpur from January to June 2011.

Results: In this cross sectional study the highest percentage of HAI (42%) belonged to the surgery ward and the lowest percentage (19.%) belonged to medicine ward of the study hospital. According to the type of infections the surgical wound infection was found on the top (23%) and the cannula-associated infection at the bottom (5%) of the list. Respondents of both the polar age groups (<21 years and > 60 years) were found to be equally (27%) affected by HAI. Occurrence of HAI was found higher (57%) among the female respondents than their male (43%) counterparts. Highest number (48%) of HAI and lowest number (14%) of non- HAI patients were found to be visited by maximum number (≥ 5) of visitors. Among the respondents who developed HAI, 42% had to stay at hospital for longest duration (21-25 days) but only 13% of their non- HAI counterparts had to stay for same duration. Among HAI patients 26% had to spend highest amount of money (Tk.20,001/- 25,000/-) but among non- HAI patients only 10% had to spend same amount of money for their treatment purpose.

Conclusion: It has been revealed from this study that the occurrence of HAI was found higher among the patients with maximum number of visitors. Average length of hospital stay and cost of treatment of HAI patients were found higher than those of their non-HAI counterparts.

Key words: Hospital Acquired Infection (HAI), Cost of treatment, Average Length of Stay (ALS).

Introduction

A "hospital acquired infection (HAI)" - has been defined by WHO as: "an infection acquired in hospital by a patient who was admitted for a reason other than that infection," or as "an infection occurring in a patient in a hospital or other health care facility in whom the infection was not present or incubating at the time of admission. This includes infections acquired in the hospital but appearing after discharge, and also occupational infections among staff of the facility."¹ The majority of HAI become evident 48 hours or more

following admission. In a study conducted by WHO in 55 hospitals of 14 countries representing 4 WHO regions (Europe, Eastern Mediterranean, South East Asia and Western Pacific) showed an average of 8.7% of hospital patients had nosocomial infections, the highest frequencies were reported from hospitals in the Eastern Mediterranean Region (11.8%) followed by South East Asia where it was 10%, with a prevalence of 7.7 and 9.0% respectively in the European and Western Pacific Regions.^{1,2} It has been revealed that at any time over 1.4 million people world-wide suffer from infectious complications.

Organism that further accentuates the problem. It has also been estimated that these infections cost more than US\$ 40 million every year in Thailand alone.³ In the prevalence studies on HAI conducted at Boston City hospital in 1964 and 1967, indicated that the prevalence was similar in both years and that surgical patients were more likely to be infected than were medical patients.⁴ A patient with a hospital infection might occupy a bed at least for three days longer than normal during which time nursing and medical staff might administer drugs and care for the patient.⁵ These

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costs could be financial, such as additional medications, travel costs or child care costs, or they could be non-financial, such as physical pain and emotional stress. Finally, if the infection delays patients or informal caregivers access to their usual activities, be they paid or un-paid, then productivity losses could accrue.

Materials and Methods

This descriptive type of cross sectional study was conducted in a tertiary level hospital of Rangpur city. The study population comprised of 200 admitted patients, among them 100 were HAI patient and 100 were non HAI. as sample of this study. All the admitted patients found present during data collection period. Data were collected through duly pre tested interviewer administered questionnaire and observation checklist. Only the Medicine, Surgery & Gynecology wards were brought under study.

Results

Among 100 HAI patients' the highest percentage 42(42%) belonged to surgery wards, 38(38%) in Gyne & Obs. wards and only 19(19%) belonged to medicine wards (Figure-1).

Figure 1: Distribution of the HAI patients by treatment areas in the hospital

According to the type of infection Surgical Wound Infection (SWI) was found on the top (25%) and Cannula-Associated Infection (CAI) was found at the bottom (6%) of the list. The occurrence of Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID) and Skin & Soft Tissue Infection (SSTI) were 20% and 16% respectively (Figure-2).

Figure 2: Distribution of the respondents by type of HAI

Equal number (27%) of HAI cases has been found among the (21-40 years) and extreme senior (61 years and above) age group. Near about the same percentage of respondents (26%) was also belonged to extreme junior (up to 20 years) age group. Lowest number (20%) of patients was found in age group of 41-60 years (Table 1)

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents by age and Types of HAI

Types of HAI	Age of the respondents in years				Total
	Up to 20	21-40	41-60	61 >	
	No. (%)	No. (%)	No. (%)	No. (%)	
Surgical wound infection	4(17.39)	6(26.08)	4(17.39)	9(39.13)	23(100.0)
Pelvic inflammatory disease	9(42.85)	5(23.80)	4(19.05)	3(14.28)	21(100.0)
Skin & soft tissue infection	4(26.67)	5(33.33)	4(26.67)	2(13.33)	15(100.0)
Urinary tract infection	1(7.14)	4(28.57)	3(21.14)	6(57.14)	14(100.0)
Respiratory tract Infection	2(15.38)	3(23.07)	4(28.57)	4(28.57)	13(100.0)
Septicemia/ Bacteremia	4(44.44)	3(33.33)	0	2(22.22)	9(100.0)
Cannula-associated infection	2(40)	1(20)	1(20)	1(20)	5(100.0)
Total	26(26)	27(27)	20(20)	27(27)	100(100.0)

Out of the 100 HAI cases 57(57%) were female and only 43(43%) of them were male. Majority (58.3%) of the respondents of surgical wound infection was male. All the (100.0%) patients of Pelvic inflammatory disease were female. Majority of the respondents affected by Skin & soft tissue infection (73.3%) and Respiratory tract Infection (60%) was male. Female majority cases were Urinary tract infection (75%) and Septicemia / Bacteremia (45.5%). Half (50.0%) of the cannula-associated infection was male and rest half was female. (Table-2)

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents by sex and Types of HAI.

Types of HAI	Sex of the respondents		Total
	Male	Female	
Surgical wound infection	14(58.33)	10(41.67%)	24(100.0%)
Pelvic inflammatory dis.	0	22(100.0%)	22(100.0%)
Skin & soft tissue infection	11 (73.33%)	4 (26.67%)	15(100.0%)
Urinary tract infection	3 (25%)	9 (75%)	12 (100.0%)
Respiratory tract Infection	6(60%)	4(40%)	10(100.0%)
Septicemia/ Bacteremia	45(45.45%)	6 (54.54%)	11 (100.0%)
Cannula-associated infection	3 (50.0%)	3 (50.0%)	6(100.0%)
Total	43 (43)	57 (57)	100 (100.0%)

It is evident from the following table that the occurrence of HAI was much more among the patients with greater number of visitors. Lowest percentage (12%) of HAI and highest percentage (44%) of non-HAI respondents were found visited by lowest number (0-1) of visitors. The number of visitors was 6 and more for 27(27%) HAI and 14(14%) non-HAI respondents (Table 3),

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by Hospital Acquired Infections and number of Visitors

Type of patients	Number of Visitors				Total
	0-1	2-3	4-5	6 and >	
HAI	12 (12)	13(13)	48 (48)	27 (27)	100 (100.0)
Non-HAI	44 (44)	26 (26)	16 (16)	14 (14)	100 (100.0)
Total	56(28.50%)	39 (19)	64 (32)	41 (21.50)	200 (100.0)

According to the following table it is evident that 6(6%) of the HAI and 50(50%) of the non- HAI respondents had to stay at hospital for shortest period (10 days and below). But 13(13 %) non-HAI patients and 42(42%)HAI patient had to stay at hospital for longest period (more than 20 days)(Table- 4)

Table 4: Distribution of the respondents by Hospital Acquired Infections and length of hospital stay

Types of patients	length of hospital stay (in days)				Total
	Up to 10	11-15	16-20	21-25	
HAI	6 (6)	11 (11)	41 (41)	42 (42)	100 (100.0)
Non-14AI	50 (50)	25(25)	12 (12)	13 (13)	100 (100.0)
Total	56 (23)	36 (18)	53 (26.50)	55(27.50)	200 (100.0)

It is evident from the following table that 12(12%) HAI and 24 (24%) non-HAI patients had to spend lowest amount of money (up to Tk.5000/-) for their treatment. Nearly one third 26 (26%) HAI and 10(10%) non-HAI patients had to spend highest amount of money (Tk.20,001- 25,000/-) for the treatment purpose (Table 5).

Table 5: Distribution of the respondents by Category of diseases and amount of extra cost.

Type of patients.	Amount of extra cost in Taka.					Total
	Up to Tk.5000/-	Tk. 5,000/- 10,000/-	Tk.10,000/- 15,000/-	Tk.15,000/- 20,000/-	Tk.20,000/- 25,000/-	
HAI	12 (12)	13 (13)	24 (24)	25 (25)	26 (26)	100 (100.0%)
Non-HAI	24(24)	38 (38)	16 (16)	12 (12)	10 (10)	100 (100.0%)
Total	36 (18)	51 (25.50)	40 (20)	37 (18.50)	36 (18)	200 (100.0%)

Discussion

In this cross sectional study in a tertiary level hospital of Rangpur City among 100 HAI patients 42(42%) belonged to the surgery ward. The HAI patients belonged to gynae ward and medicine ward were 38(38%) and 19(19%) respectively. According to the type of HAI, surgical wound infection was found on the top (23%) and cannula-associated infection was found at the bottom (5%) of the list. This distribution of HAI is consistent with the findings of the study conducted by Khan MH in 2003.⁷He also detected the surgical wound infection as the major cause of HAI, and Urinary Tract Infection as the second major cause. Regarding age distribution, though the difference was not statistically significant but respondents of two polar age groups were found more infected than their counterpart of middle age group. Hussain T et al in their study also found that age and sex distribution of HAI cases were not statistically significant, but the rate of HAI was more in the extremes of ages. It has been revealed from the study that the occurrence of HAI was much more among patients with greater number of visitors. The number of visitors was 6 and more for 27% HAI and 14% non-HAI respondents respectively. This study depicts that majority of the non-HAI patients were visited by minimum number (0-1) of visitors per day. A similar finding was revealed in Tahmina's study⁹, she found that the prevalence of HAI was 37.5% among the patients who were visited by 9 visitors per day, whereas the prevalence was 21.8% among those patients who had least number of visitors (0-2) per day.⁶ This study revealed that patients with HAI had to stay for longer period in hospital than their non-HAI counterpart for treatment purpose. Hadi in his comparative study found that average length of hospital stay for HAI patients was 27.5days.⁸ The shorter period of hospital stay found in this study indicate the improvement of hospital care at least to some extent. It has also been shown in the present study that the patients with HAI had to spend more money for their treatment than their non-HAI counterpart. Among all of them 26% HAI patients had to spend taka 20,000/- -25000/- but only 10% non-HAI patients had to spend that amount for treatment purpose. Khan (2000) found in his study that the majority (38.29%) of the respondents spent TK 10000/- -20000/- as extra cost for HAI. Mean extra cost was Tk. 20,435/- with SD± 15,750.¹⁵⁷

Conclusion

Comparing the findings of the present study with that of the previous studies it is evident that the occurrence of the Hospital Acquired Infections is lower than that of the previous study. In spite of this attention should be given to operation theater and post operative zones, because surgical wound infection was still found on the top of the list among all HAI. Hospitals should also provide special care to the respondents of extreme junior and extreme senior age groups, because they were found to be more infected than their middle aged counterpart. This study depicts a high level of extra cost during the stay at hospital that could be averted by minimizing the occurrence of HAIs. Respondents with higher number of visitors were found to be affected more by HAI than their counterpart who had least number of visitors, so flow of visitors should be restricted for minimizing the prevalence of HAI.

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Porcelain laminate veneer – a conservative treatment in restoration of anterior teeth defect

F Rashid

Abstract

In this study, 100% of the patients were satisfied aesthetically after 6 months and 12 months. 100% patients presented without the complaint of sensitivity after 6 and 12 months. 100% of the patients presented with healthy periodontium after 6 and 12 months. De bonding and porcelain fracture were found in 10% in both the cases after 12 months. No complaint against aesthetic and sensitivity was recorded after 12 months.

Keywords: Porcelain laminate veneer; aesthetics, anterior tooth defect, conventional crown.

Introduction

A defect in anterior teeth requires special attention to aesthetic. Currently porcelain laminate veneer is the most durable aesthetic material to correct those that are discolored, miss-happened or damaged. Porcelain laminate veneer is probably the most aesthetic means of creating a more pleasing and beautiful smile.¹ In many cases veneers are applied instead of mostly and invasive crowns.²

Veneers are a permanent process and should therefore only be considered by individuals that have all of their permanent teeth. Porcelain laminate veneers are extremely thin pieces of Ceramic material that are permanently attached to the front of a patient's teeth using a Composite resin as bonding cement³, in order to enhance the union between the tooth and Porcelain laminate veneer, the development of acid – etching of enamel to improve the retention of resin first described by Buonocore⁴, which attaching veneers to the teeth by less destructive means. The inner surface of the porcelain laminate veneer is treated with hydrofluoric acid etching till its frosty white and increasing the surface area with retentive irregularities for a mechanical bond to composite.

Aesthetic veneer should always be considered as a conservative alternative to cemented crowns. In many practices, they have largely replaced metal ceramic crowns.⁵ Un-questionably; one of the disadvantages of conventional crown is the destruction of tooth structure. An advantage of this approach is the saving of tooth structure, laboratory time and materials, thus giving a possible cost advantage.

Materials and Methods

This prospective study was conducted in the Department of Prosthodontics, Faculty of Dentistry, Banghabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), Shahbag, Dhaka from January 2004 to December 2005. 30 patients were selected who attended in this department for treatment of discolored anterior teeth, abrasion, erosion, minor mal-alignment and anterior teeth diastema as the subjects of this study. Each patient was evaluated by a thorough medical and dental history as well as clinical and radiographic examination.

According to patient's concern he or she was selected for the treatment and tooth preparation was done. A minimum 0.5mm labial tooth surface reduction should be done which follow the anatomic contours of tooth. Interproximal preparation reached the facial aspect of the contact area to ensure that the margin between veneer and tooth surface was not visible. Enamel was preserved in the interproximal contact area. The incisal edge was extended lingually only if a diastema or minor mal- alignment of anterior tooth was recorded. An accurate impression of the prepared teeth was taken with elastomeric impression and master cast was poured. A refractory was made by the duplication of master cast by type 4 dental stone.

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Die spacer was applied to the labial surfaces and 2mm was short of the finish line. Porcelain was build-up incrementally and contoured with the reference to the study model which was taken before tooth preparation. Porcelain powder build-up was done in layers for firing (Firing was done above 900°C).

After completion of build-up, firing and contouring, the refractory dies were separated individually by a thin diamond disc. The veneer was then glazed. The final prosthesis was cemented on etched tooth surface and restoration was seated with a composite resin luting agent. Having cemented patients were advised to attend after 6 and 12 months for the evaluation of both the prosthesis and associated oral tissues. Data collection was done according to specific parameters like esthetics, sensitivity development, periodontal disease, marginal integrity, porcelain fracture and de-bonding. The findings were recorded in a pre-designed data collection sheet.

Results

The table shows the variables and results recorded in this study after 6 months and 12 months.

Variables	After 6 months		After 12 months	
	Affected % (No)	Not affected % (No)	Affected % (No)	Not affected % (No)
Aesthetics	00 (00)	100 (30)	00 (00)	100 (30)
Sensitivity	00 (00)	100 (30)	00 (00)	100 (30)
Periodontal diseases	00 (00)	100 (30)	00 (00)	100 (30)
Marginal integrity	00 (00)	100 (30)	10 (03)	90 (27)
Porcelain fracture	6.7 (02)	93.3 (28)	10 (03)	90 (27)
De-bonding	00 (00)	90 (30)	10 (03)	90 (27)

In this study total 30 patients were treated with porcelain laminate veneer to find out any complications in one year. After 6 months only 6.7% patients of porcelain laminate veneer were affected by porcelain fracture. No patient complained about their aesthetic, sensitivity, periodontal disease after 6 and 12 months.

After 12 months of cementation there was no alteration of marginal integrity in case of 90% of the patients and 10% patients had alteration of marginal integrity. Porcelain fracture and debonding occurred in 10% cases after 12 months. No patient complained about the aesthetic as there was no mis-match in color, shade and translucence between restoration and adjacent teeth.

Discussion

Majority of the patients in this study was female, a similar finding was also reported in other clinical evaluation on porcelain laminate veneers. This suggests that, in general, females might be more interested in their appearance that improves esthetics.⁶ A research organization has stated that Porcelain veneers will become an “accepted procedure” that promises “the highest esthetics potential to date for restoration of anterior tooth defect.”⁷

100% of the patients presented without the complain of sensitivity after 12 months which is very advantageous point for porcelain laminate veneer. There was alteration of marginal integrity in case of 10% of the patients. Herbert Dumfahrt et al showed in a study that marginal integrity was acceptable in 99% cases among 191 patients and excellent in 63% case.⁸ After a year of cementation 10% of the patients treated with porcelain laminate veneer presented with debonded prosthesis and other 90% were not affected. Swift *et al* reported that shear bond strength of composite luted to silanded porcelain laminate veneers would not be significantly affected by saliva or latex glove contamination.⁹ Other studies show that saliva contamination of either etched enamel or porcelain will reduced its bond strength to composite significantly.¹⁰

Conclusion

It can be concluded that the Porcelain Laminate veneer is an advantageous restoration for the improvement of aesthetic in anterior teeth which has minor surface defect, abrasion, erosion and discoloration as it is more conservative.

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Efficacy of Two Rotary Instruments For Gutta Percha Removal During Root Canal Retreatment

JS Dhillon¹, A Bhagat², G Chhabra³

Abstract

Aim - Evaluate the efficacy of ProTaper and ProTaper Retreatment instruments in the removal of gutta-percha during retreatment of straight root canals in comparison with Hedstrom files.

Methodology -The root canals of 30 Maxillary central incisors were instrumented by step back procedure and obturated with lateral condensation before the teeth were randomly divided into three groups of 10 specimens each i.e. Group 1-using H files, Group 2- using ProTaper and Group 3- using ProTaper retreatment. Radiographs were taken after the filling removal and the canal wall cleanliness was evaluated. Roots were divided into apical, middle and coronal parts and scored on a scale of 0 (no debris), 1(25-50% of walls covered with debris and 3 (>50% of walls covered with debris).Number of fractured instruments were also evaluated in each group.

Results -There was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) between the three groups in terms of the debris seen radio graphically after retreatment.

Conclusion - All systems evaluated ex vivo were equally effective in removing gutta percha during retreatment.

Keywords: Retreatment, fractured, efficacy, obturated, debris

Introduction

Root canal therapy, despite having a high degree of success, may not lead to the desired response, and failure may occur¹⁻⁵. When root canal therapy fails, treatment options include conventional retreatment, periradicular surgery or extraction. Whenever possible, the retreatment option is preferred because it is the most conservative method to solve the problem⁶. Nonsurgical endodontic retreatment is an attempt to re-establish healthy periapical tissues after inefficient treatment or re-infection of an obturated root canal system because of coronal or apical leakage.

It requires regaining access to the entire root canal system through removal of the original root canal filling, further cleaning and reobturation⁷. Posts or broken instruments can be removed using specific technologies⁸.

Removal of gutta-percha and sealer is an important factor in root canal retreatment. Necrotic tissues or bacteria, covered by remaining gutta-percha or sealer, maybe responsible for periapical inflammation or pain. Most frequently Enterococcus faecalis, followed by Streptococcus spp. and Tannerella forsythensis was found in poorly root-filled teeth associated with periradicular lesions⁹. Thus, as much obturation material as possible has to be removed to uncover residual bacteria. This enables thorough chemomechanical re-instrumentation and re-disinfection of the root canal system¹⁰.

Gutta-percha removal can be achieved by several methods. One of these methods is the chemical technique, using different types of solvents, such as chloroform, eucalyptol, xylene, halothane, turpentine, or orange solvent, in combination with K-type or Hedstrom file¹¹⁻¹⁶. Care should be taken to avoid forcing the softened gutta-percha or solvent through the apical foramen to avoid periradicular tissue irritation¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Other methods of gutta-percha removal include removing the coronal portion of gutta-percha using Gates Glidden or heat pluggers²⁰, then the rest can be removed by an ultrasonic technique^{21,22}.

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Additionally, rotary instruments can also be used, such as the inflexible GPX burs²³, the canal finder²⁴⁻²⁶, or one of the recent flexible rotary nickel-titanium (NiTi) files in a slow-speed handpiece^{27,28}.

Removal of GP using hand files with or without solvents is time-consuming, especially when the filling materials are well condensed^{29,30}. Nickel-titanium (Ni-Ti) rotary instruments have been used successfully in root canal cleaning and shaping. ProTaper files are characterized by progressively increasing tapers, a convex triangular cross-section, and a modified guiding tip^{28,29}. Schirrmeister *et al.*^{31,32} showed no difference between the ProTaper and hand instrumentation in gutta-percha removal in straight and curved root canals. This technique yielded a high-fracture incidence of 22.7%³¹.

More recently, the ProTaper Ni-Ti rotary system has been upgraded to the ProTaper Universal system, which includes shaping, finishing and retreatment instruments. The three retreatment instruments (D1, D2 and D3) are designed for removing filling materials from root canals. They have various tapers and diameters at the tip, which are size 30, 0.09 taper, size 25, 0.08 taper and size 20, 0.07 taper. The full lengths of these retreatment files are 16 mm for D1, 18 mm for D2 and 22 mm for D3. D1, D2 and D3 are recommended to remove filling materials from the coronal, middle and apical portions of canals respectively. Similar to the shaping and finishing instruments, the retreatment series have a convex cross section, however, D1 has a working tip that facilitates its initial penetration into filling materials. The purpose of the present laboratory study was to evaluate the efficacy of ProTaper Universal retreatment files in removing GP from root canals.

Materials and Methods

Thirty extracted maxillary central incisors with a single straight canal, verified radiographically, and with completely formed apices were selected. Access cavities were prepared and working lengths determined prior to the canals being prepared with a step-back technique with normal saline irrigation. The canals were enlarged with K-type files (DentsplyMaillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) to a size 50 at working length. The canals were obturated with a zinc oxide eugenol sealer (SS White, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil) and lateral condensation of gutta-percha. The access openings were sealed with a temporary filling material (Cimpat - Septodont, Saint-Maur-des-Fosses, France) and the teeth were stored at 37 °C in 100% humidity for 2 days.

Bucco-lingual and mesio-distal radiographs (Eastman Kodak, Rochester, NY, USA) were taken using radio-visiography (RVG) to examine the quality of obturation and, in particular, the apical extent and degree of condensation. The distance between the X-ray source (XR6010 Gnatus, Ribeirao Preto, Brazil) and the sensor (Satelec, digital xray system, sotoacteon) and the direction of the beam were the same throughout the study. The exposure time was 0.2 s. The teeth were randomly divided into three groups with 10 specimens each. The temporary fillings were removed and the root canals reopened.

GROUP A:

D1, D2 and D3 were sequentially used in a crown-down manner to reach the pre-established WL; they were manipulated in a brushing action. The rotational speed was set at 500 rpm as recommended. It was followed by cleaning of the apex with Hedstrom files up to size 50 and no circumferential filing was done.

GROUP B:

ProTaper Universal rotary shaping (S1 and S2) and finishing (F1, F2 and F3) instruments, which were used in a gentle brushing action at a speed of 300 rpm according to the manufacturers' instructions. It was followed by cleaning of the apex with Hedstrom files up to size 50 and no circumferential filing was done.

GROUP C:

Hedstrom files (DentsplyMaillefer) sizes 80, 70, 60, 50 were used in a circumferential quarter-turn push-pull filing motion to remove the root fillings from the middle and apical portions until the original WL had been reached.

When ProTaper Universal retreatment files are used to remove GP, slight apical pressure has to be exerted for file penetration. Files should be withdrawn frequently for the removal of the debris from instrument flutes before being reintroduced in the root canal system. If the rotary instruments fail to progress along the canal path, stainless steel hand files may be used to check the resistance and establish the glide path.

Retreatment was considered to be complete when gutta-percha removal stopped and no gutta-percha could be observed in the access opening. Bucco-lingual and proximal views of each retreated root were used by the observer to gauge how much debris (gutta-percha/sealer) remained; this was compared with the example radiographs and a score given.

Radiographs were recorded by the same observer 1 week later using the same method to check reproducibility.

Observers were asked to give one of the following scores for each third of the root canal: 0 = if no radio-opaque debris could be observed; 1 = <25% debris; 2 = 25 – 50% debris; 3 = >50% debris. Bucco-lingual and proximal views of each retreated root were used by the observers to gauge how much debris (gutta-percha/sealer) remained; this was compared with the example radiographs and a score given. The number of fractured instruments was recorded for each group.

Data were analyzed using a Stata Version 5.0 with significance predetermined at a level of 0.05. The Kruskal–Wallis test was used to estimate inter-observer correlation and to compare the difference between retreatment groups at the three levels. The Mann-Whitney test was done to compare the difference between the coronal apical and middle third of the canals in all the three groups.

Results

There was no significant difference between examiner’s assessments at each recording session. Therefore the data were pooled.

Table-1 displaying the probability values using Kruskal– Wallis analysis to determine differences between each method of retreatment at the three levels

BL/MD	GROUP		N	MEAN	SD	MIN.	MAX.	PERCENTILE		
								25th	50th	75th
BL	PROTAPER RETREATMENT	cor	10	1.40	.516	1	2	1.00	1.00	2.00
		mid	10	1.00	.000	1	1	1.00	1.00	1.00
		api	10	1.00	.667	0	2	.75	1.00	1.25
	PROTAPER	cor	10	1.70	.675	0	2	1.75	2.00	2.00
		mid	10	1.00	.568	0	2	.75	1.00	1.00
		api	10	0.90	.816	0	3	.75	1.00	1.00
	HAND	cor	10	1.90	.568	1	3	1.75	2.00	2.00
		mid	10	1.30	.675	1	3	1.25	1.00	1.00
		api	10	1.00	.816	0	3	.75	1.00	1.00
MD	PROTAPER RETREATMENT	cor	10	1.40	.516	1	2	1.00	1.00	2.00
		mid	10	.80	.632	0	2	0.00	1.00	1.00
		api	10	.90	.568	0	2	.75	1.00	1.00
	PROTAPER	cor	10	1.40	.843	0	3	1.00	1.00	2.00
		mid	10	.90	.738	0	2	0.00	1.00	1.25
		api	10	.70	.483	0	1	0.00	1.00	1.00
	HAND	cor	10	1.50	.707	0	2	1.00	2.00	2.00
		mid	10	1.10	.316	1	2	1.00	1.00	1.00
		api	10	.70	.675	0	2	0.00	1.00	1.00

Table 1 displays the probability values using Kruskal–Wallis analysis to determine differences between each method of retreatment at the three levels. No significant difference was found between the three groups.

Table-2 showing the results of Mann-Whitney test showing significant difference between coronal and middle third of the canals in all the three groups

BL/MD	GROUP	Z	COR-MID	COR-API	API-MID
BL	PROTAPER RETREATMENT	Z	-2.000(a)	-1.633(a)	0.000(a)
		Asymp. Sig (2 tailed)	.046	.102	0.000
	PROTAPER	Z	-2.828(a)	-2.333(a)	.447(c)
		Asymp. Sig (2 tailed)	.005	.020	.655
	HAND	Z	-2.161(a)	-2.460(a)	-1.732(a)
		Asymp. Sig (2 tailed)	.034	.014	.083
MD	PROTAPER RETREATMENT	Z	-2.449(a)	-1.899(a)	-.577(c)
		Asymp. Sig (2 tailed)	.014	.059	.564
	PROTAPER	Z	-2.236(a)	-2.333(a)	1.414(c)
		Asymp. Sig (2 tailed)	.025	.020	.157
	HAND	Z	-1.633(a)	-2.530(a)	-2.000(a)
		Asymp. Sig (2 tailed)	.102	.011	.046

Table 2 showing the results of Mann-Whitney test shows significant difference between coronal and middle third of the canals in all the three groups. Significant difference was also seen in coronal and apical third of the canals in group B and group C. All of these showed more debris in the coronal third as compared to the apical and middle third. Only 1 instrument fractured in group B unlike Group A and Group C where no instrument fracture was observed.

Discussion

Complete removal of pre-existing filling material from canals is a prerequisite for successful nonsurgical root canal retreatment³². This procedure can uncover residual necrotic tissues or bacteria that may be responsible for persistent periapical inflammation, and allow further cleaning and refilling of the root canal system^{33,34}. Remaining filling debris has been assessed by radiography^{34,35}, splitting teeth longitudinally^{36,37} or making teeth transparent^{31,32,34,38}. Radiographs are limited to two-dimensions. Ideally, three-dimensional visualization of the root canal system would provide a better understanding of the distribution of the debris after retreatment. Micro-computed tomography may be a viable alternative for the qualitative and quantitative evaluation of retreatment procedures³⁹. The radiographic technique produced magnification with good resolution that would be impossible by conventional dental radiography. By examining the teeth from two views at right angles to each other an overall impression of the amount of debris remaining could be obtained.

As it has been shown in the literature, it was impossible to remove all traces of GP/sealer from root canals with any retreatment technique, regardless of single or combined action^{29,40,41}. This was also demonstrated in the present study, as none of the specimens was free of GP/sealer remnants.

All the retreatment procedures in this study left more debris coronally than apically. This might be because the use of Gates Glidden drills is a well known technique for gutta-percha removal from the coronal and middle parts of the root canal and these files have not been used in this study. Just the use of any of the file systems could not clean the coronal area completely. This is contrary to previous studies which show that apical area is most difficult to clean especially in curved canals⁴².

This study was performed on endodontic teeth with straight root canals. Therefore, the conclusions of this study could not be directly extended to teeth with curved root canals. However, more ProTaper files fractured during retreatment of curved canals compared with straight canals. Clearly, more studies are needed to evaluate the efficacy, maintenance of original canal morphology, and safety of rotary Ni-Ti instruments during retreatment of teeth with complicated root canal anatomy.

It was only possible to make a semi quantitative evaluation of the amount of debris remaining. Evaluation was subjective, and observer performance is known to be variable in many cases where diagnosis is required.

Prior to the introduction of ProTaper Universal retreatment files, ProTaper rotary finishing files had been used for GP removal (27, 38). This technique yielded a high-fracture incidence of 22.7% (38). Procedural errors including instrument fracture were not noted in the present study, demonstrating the safety of ProTaper Universal retreatment instruments in endodontic retreatment. As a general rule, Ni-Ti rotary instruments should be used with great caution.

Conclusion

It should be kept in mind that the clinical outcome of endodontic treatment is significantly affected by pre-operative diagnoses but not by the specific choice of an instrumentation system. The results of the present study suggest that all systems evaluated *ex vivo* were equally effective in removing gutta percha during retreatment.

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Self-reported Oral and Dental Health Status among the Pregnant Women of A Selected Hospital in Dhaka City

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Abstract

Aims: The aims of this study were to gain an understanding of pregnant women's oral hygiene practices and to assess the oral and dental health status.

Materials and Methods: A semi - structured questionnaire was completed by 100 pregnant women of the gynecology department of Dr. Akhter Jahan Mirza Hospital, Dhaka.

Results: The women in this study 40% were in 19-22 years age group. Forty eight percent (48%) women of the subjects were having up to high school level education & 28% had low income of Sixty Thousand to One Lac taka yearly. In relation to oral hygiene habit before pregnancy majority of the women (56%) stated that they brush their teeth once a day, 19% use dental floss and 14% use mouth rinse once a day. During pregnancy women seemed to be slightly more concerned about oral hygiene but not significantly. Only 66% brush their teeth and 17% floss their teeth and 18% use mouth rinse once a day during pregnancy. The major problem in their mouth noticed by the women during pregnancy was bleeding gums (58%).

Conclusion: This study feels the necessity of giving special attention to pregnant women's oral health in Bangladesh. Women should be educated on good oral hygiene practices so as to minimize prevalence of poor maternal oral health during pregnancy.

Key words: Pregnancy, Oral hygiene, Dental knowledge.

Introduction

Pregnancy is a unique time in women's life and is characterized by complex physiological changes. These changes can adversely affect oral health.

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Therefore, the pregnant population group requires special care in terms of oral health care including nutrition. Pregnancy has no direct causation on tooth loss, but there are a number of factors that influence the rapidity and progression of incipient or already well-established oral disease. The expectant mother may be involved in a multitude of extra activities, which can lead to a neglect of her own oral care and can result in dental problems which require extra attention during this phase.

Hormonal changes during pregnancy have been suggested to predispose women to gingivitis, affecting 35-100% of pregnant women¹⁵. Mainly because of estrogen, the gum become inflamed, edematous, and sensitive, with a tendency to bleed easily, and existing gingivitis may worsen considerably during pregnancy if plaque is not removed^{4,8}. Furthermore, advanced periodontal infections in pregnant women may pose a threat to the placenta and uterus and may increase the likelihood of pre-term delivery^{3,14}. It has been estimated that periodontal disease of the mother might cause more than 18% of all pre-term births and low birth weight in infants¹⁴.

Support for dental treatment in governmental hospitals is not enough in district levels in Bangladesh. Mothers and children welfare center (MCWC) is a sister organization of Bangladesh government under the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, where the antenatal women come for regular checkup.

They have dental problems but in MCWCs have no support for dental treatment¹².

It has been recommended that all women should have a dental examination and appropriate dental hygiene care at least once during their pregnancy¹. However, many women in a number of countries do not visit a dentist during their pregnancy^{5,6,11}. Therefore oral and dental health care practices and knowledge of pregnant women in Bangladesh should be assessed as a high risk group.

So, this study was planned to describe the self-reported oral hygiene practices and to assess the oral and dental health status among the pregnant women in gynecology department of Dr. Akhter Jahan Mirza Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Materials and Methods

A descriptive cross - sectional study was carried out among pregnant women attending at gynecology department of Dr. Akhter Jahan Mirza Hospital, Dhaka. The sample size was 100 pregnant women. The time period of the study was limited to six months. Within this period, eight weeks were spent for data collection and the rest of the period were spent for analysis, report writing and submission. Purposive sampling technique was followed for selection of the study women. A semi-structured questionnaire was developed following a pilot study in a small similar study population. The one-to-one interview was taken as per the printed questionnaire. Security and confidentiality was maintained by taking appropriate care and sincerity of interviewers and the researcher as per ethical consideration of the research. After completion of data collection all questionnaires were filed up, statistical software SPSS (vesion 15.0) was used to enter data for analysis. Prior to commencement of the study, ethical clearance was taken from Ethical Review Committee (ERC, No. 10-91195) of American International University-Bangladesh (AIUB).

Results

A total of 100 pregnant women were examined. The age groups were divided into five categories, of which 40% were in the age group of 19-22 years. Others were 15-18 years 16%, 23-27 years 15%, 28-35 years 17%, and 35+ years age 12%. [Figure-1]

Figure -1 Different Age group

The education groups were divided into “less than high school” category (which includes ability to sign own name to primary school level), “high school” category (which includes class 6 to SSC pass) “diploma”, “graduate” and “postgraduate” category. Almost half of the women studied had less than High School education (48%) [Figure-2].

Figure – 2 Level of Education

About household income, 28% of the study women had a low (60,000-1 lac taka) annual income and 26% did not know their household income [Figure-3].

Figure- 3 Annual Family Incomes

In non-pregnant stage 56% and during pregnant stage 66% stated that they brush their teeth once a day and also it was found that 58% of the women in non-pregnant stage and 52% of women in pregnant stage never flossed their teeth. 14% of the women used mouth wash in non-pregnant stage and 18% in pregnant stage. However, comparing the dental hygiene before and during their pregnancy period it shows that during pregnancy women seemed to be slightly more concerned about oral hygiene but not significantly [Table-1].

Table-1 The oral hygiene status before and during pregnancy period

Variables	Before pregnancy	Current Pregnancy
How often brush your teeth	Percentage	Percentage
Twice or more a day	19	29
Once a day	56	66
Not every day	25	5
How often floss your teeth		
Twice or more a day	8	12
Once a day	19	17
Not every day	15	19
Never	58	52
Use mouth rinse		
Yes	14	18
No	86	82

The major problem in their mouth noticed by the women during pregnancy was bleeding gums 58%, toothache 13%, cavities 7%, and sensitive teeth 4% [Figure-4].

Figure – 4 Changes in teeth/gum during pregnancy

Discussion

A number of self-reported studies around the world have investigated about the level of dental care, dental health access and knowledge about dental health and their relationship with pregnancy outcomes^{2, 5, 7, 9, 16}.

So far this is the first study in Bangladesh adopting a similar approach. Previously, Makowharemahihi presented a thesis on “A community-based health needs assessment of the oral health needs of Maori mothers in Porirua”, in which she extrapolated through a qualitative study the needs of a group of Maori mothers¹⁰.

The present study, sought to provide more broadly quantitative information about expectant mothers in the gynae department of Dr. Akhtar Jahan Mirza Hospital, Dhaka. The main finding of this research on pregnant women participating in this study presented with poor oral hygiene habits, more than half of the women reported bleeding gums during pregnancy. The first objective of this research was to analyze oral health care practices and behavior of women before and during pregnancy, and whether these changed during this period. This was achieved through a series of questions relevant to dentistry including oral hygiene.

In this study, most women reported “fair” & “poor” oral hygiene, brush their teeth one time per day, use floss and mouth wash occasionally. Their hygiene pattern did not change significantly during pregnancy, with 29% brush their teeth twice or more per day, 12% flossed their teeth once a day and 18% using mouth rinse. Other international studies show similar findings of oral hygiene during pregnancy, but these studies did not compare this with oral hygiene practices before pregnancy^{7, 15}.

The main change and/or problems related to mouths that were reported by women during pregnancy were bleeding gums, followed by sensitive teeth and others (such as infections or broken teeth). It is important to note that 58% of women in this study noticed bleeding gums during pregnancy. Similar findings were observed in the Australian study¹⁶ where 60% of the women stated that they had gums bleeding at some stage during the previous 12 months. Bleeding gums is normally one of the first signs of gingivitis and is common among pregnant women due to hormonal changes in this period which accentuate the gum’s response to plaque. It is important to point out that pregnancy does not cause gingivitis, but may aggravate pre-existing disease. However, gingivitis can progress to periodontitis (loss of connective tissue)¹³ and, according to a number of studies; can be associated with birth outcomes¹⁴ such as low birth weight, preterm birth and preeclampsia. Similar frequencies were observed in a number of international researches, 30% in Australia¹⁶, a range of 25- 50% in American studies^{5, 9}.

There is a lack of formal guideline about oral health for pregnant women in Bangladesh, which could be beneficial for public and health professionals to inform pregnant woman about the best practices regarding this topic. The other sources of information for pregnant woman in our study were dental healthcare workers and maternity careers.

Finally, there is a lack of integration between dentistry and other professional areas such as maternity care workers, who do not normally cover this topic with their patients. Sometimes dentists are insecure about the management of pregnant patients and don’t take the opportunity to promote preventative measures.

The vast majority of women receive antenatal care from midwives, obstetrician and attend antenatal classes. Thus, maternity careers are in a strategic position to provide counseling to pregnant women regarding oral health. Women could be advised to see the dentist before becoming pregnant and visit the dentist and other dental health workers during pregnancy, especially for checkup and cleaning. They should be advised to brush their teeth at least twice a day, floss at least once a day and have a balanced diet avoiding excessive amount of sugary snack.

Conclusions

This study feels the necessity of special attention to pregnant women's oral health in Bangladesh. From this study, we can conclude that majority of the pregnant women had a poor level of oral hygiene with gingivitis. So, dental health education programs should be carried out at regular intervals to impart knowledge on dental health and oral hygiene practices. The dentist should be consulted as early as possible in the first stages of pregnancy for a thorough examination so that all necessary treatments can be carried out well in advance.

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Laser Treatment Based on Minimal Intervention – Report of Cases

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Abstract

Since the development of the ruby laser by Maiman in 1960, many lasers are available today for clinical application in dentistry, based on minimally invasive (MI) dental treatment in routine clinical procedures including dental cavity preparation, removal of dental calculus, caries prevention, and treatment of dentin hypersensitivity, anti-inflammation for soft tissues, pain relief, surgical operations, and hemostasis. Dental treatment using a laser is a minimally invasive, painless treatment with a low burden on the patient, and may therefore be seen as a treatment that complies with the MI concept. However, safe use of lasers must be the underlying goal of proposed or future laser therapy. To ensure that safe, effective MI treatment is practiced when using lasers, it is essential to have a full understanding of their advantages and disadvantages before using them.

Key words: Laser, Minimal Intervention, Caries Removal, Removal of Melanin Pigmentation.

Introduction

There has recently been a rapid spread of treatments using lasers in the field of dentistry^{1, 2}. Lasers are now widely used in minimally invasive (MI) dental treatment in routine clinical procedures including dental cavity preparation³, removal of dental calculus⁴, caries

prevention⁵, treatment of dentin hypersensitivity⁶, anti-inflammation for soft tissues⁷, pain relief, surgical operations⁸, and hemostasis.

Laser is an acronym for "light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation"¹. Einstein put forward his theory of stimulated emission in 1917, and Maiman successfully generated a ruby laser beam in 1960. Since then, many different types of lasers have been developed. A laser beam is light, which is a type of electromagnetic wave and has the characteristics of coherence (wavelength and phase are uniform), monochromacy, directionality (the beam is straight without spreading out), condensability, and high output capability. The laser can have thermal and non-thermal (photochemical) effects on an irradiated body. Non-thermal effects may be further classified as photic stimulation, photochemical effects, photo-dissociation effects, and photo impact wave effects. These effects depend mainly on the energy and the wavelength of the laser. For example, lasers with wavelengths in the infrared region, such as the CO₂ laser (10.6 μm), Er:YAG laser (2.94 μm), or Nd:YAG laser (1.06 μm), mainly produce thermal effects. The sudden rise in temperature of the exposed area causes effects such as ablation or solidification in tissues such as dental hard tissue. Lasers with wavelengths in the ultraviolet region, such as the excimer laser (0.248 μm), have non-thermal effects and can be used in applications such as pain relief. Lasers with wavelengths in the visible ray region, such as the He-Ne laser (0.633 μm) and diode laser (0.655–0.900 μm)⁹, have both effects and are used in applications such as pain relief and photodynamic therapy (PDT). Diode lasers are also used at high power for surgical operations and solidification.

CO₂ and Er:YAG lasers show surface absorbency, whereas Nd:YAG, diode, and He-Ne lasers are able to penetrate tissues. These characteristics need to be taken into account in the use of lasers.

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Here, we used routinely encountered cases to explain approaches to operative and cosmetic dental treatment with lasers based on the concept of minimal invasion, which is our area of specialty, and examined the significance of such approaches.

Figure 1 - LASERS

A: DIAGNodent Pen (KaVo), B: Erwin AdvErL EvoMorita, C: Super Pulse Laser LX-20SPLUXAR

Case 1 (Figs. 1A, 1B, 2)

The patient was a 23-year-old man who attended the clinic for a regular checkup. Coloration was found in the pit and fissure of the occlusal surface of the maxillary left second molar. There was no symptom in particular (Fig. 2). As there were no clear findings from X-ray examination, an examination for caries was carried out by the laser fluorescence method¹⁰. The resulting diagnosis was that restorative treatment was needed from the central pit along the buccal groove, and preventative treatment was needed in the distal pit. Ablation of dental hard tissue was carried out under running water by using the Erwin AdvErL Evo Er:YAG laser (Morita Corp.)¹¹ at 10 pps and 150 mJ, after which restorative treatment was carried out by using the Bond Force one-step bonding system and the Estelite Flow Quick/Estelite Σ Quick system (Tokuyama Dental Corp.). Laser fluorescence is a method for examining dental caries by irradiating healthy and carious dental hard tissue with a diode laser (655 nm) and measuring the difference in intensity of the fluorescence reflection. Laser fluorescence can be used effectively and non-invasively for follow-up observations and for determining dental hard tissue that needs preventative or restorative treatment, and it is a highly accurate and reproducible method of examination. Also, as Er:YAG lasers show strong absorption in water, they react with the hydration sphere of a hydroxyapatite surface to produce heat, and the tiny blasts (ablation) from this heat together with the photo impact effect of the pulse wave (photo-mechanical process) can cut tooth tissue. The smear layer on the surface of the dentine produced when cutting with a rotary drilling device does not form when using lasers. However, a denatured layer forms, which works unfavorably for bonding, so this layer needs to be removed with a spoon excavator before bonding.

Figure 2 Case 1

A: First visit (#27) B: Caries diagnosis by Laser fluorescence method
C: Result of diagnosis D: After treatment (composite resin restoration in buccal fissure after caries removal using Er:YAG laser and preventive care in distal pit)

Case 2 (Fig. 1C, Fig. 3)

The patient was a 24-year-old woman, who attended the clinic with the main complaint of poor esthetic appearance of the gums. The woman was a smoker (Fig. 3). The patient was diagnosed with melanin pigmentation, and after she was given guidance in giving up smoking, the areas of gum discoloration in the upper and lower jaw were removed under surface anesthesia by irradiation with a Super Pulse Laser LX-20SP CO₂ laser (LUXAR)¹² using a ceramic tip at 4 W and a continuous wave. At around 3 postoperative days, she experienced stinging pain on the surface of the gums, but no other problems were found. The same treatment was carried out after an interval of 10–14 days, and as the patient was satisfied, the treatment was brought to completion. CO₂ lasers have thermal effects on tissues, and the sudden rise in temperature of the irradiated area causes ablation and solidification. Because the gums of the front teeth are thin, the effects of thermal stimulation on the surrounding tissues need to be taken carefully into account.

Figure 3 Case 2

A: First visit
B: Removal of melanin pigmentation with CO₂ laser
C: Re-irradiation after 14 days
D: After 6 months

Discussion

When used for caries treatment, lasers have the huge advantage that they mitigate the fear of dental treatment because they have none of the unpleasant noise and vibration of rotary drilling devices. Also, as anesthesia is not normally needed, lasers have the advantage that they can be used without anxiety for patients suffering systemic disorders such as high blood pressure. Lasers can be used to carry out caries treatment easily on patients with small mouths such as young children, and because little heat is produced while cutting, treatment can be carried out while the tooth pulp is kept in check with a small amount of running water. Also, lasers have advantages when used on soft tissues in that they suppress bleeding, have sterilizing and detoxification effects, increase the rate of healing, and cause little postoperative pain. The disadvantages include the time it takes to cut through tooth tissue, roughness of the cut surface, the high cost of equipment, and the possible risks if the safety management is not perfect. In particular, to ensure safety when lasers are used, laser equipment must, of course, be inspected before use and properly maintained, and staff must have safety training. In addition, special protective glasses must be worn to prevent any damage to the retina, cornea, or crystalline lens, and care must be taken to ensure as far as possible that the skin is not exposed to the laser.

Conclusion

As we have noted here, dental treatment using a laser is a minimally invasive, painless treatment with a low burden on the patient, and may therefore be seen as a treatment that complies with the MI concept. To ensure that safe, effective MI treatment is practiced when using lasers, it is essential to have a full understanding of their advantages and disadvantages before using them.

Lasers have been in use in medicine for no more than half a century. During this time, the development of lasers and the accumulation of evidence-based medicine using them have been astonishing. For example, there is great interest these days in CAD/CAM and 3D printers using lasers.

There have also been advances in the analyses of biological effects and mechanisms and in the development of new methods of diagnosis and treatment using lasers. Lasers are likely to develop further as the "dream light" for next-generation dental treatments.

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Infection Control Measures in Some Selected Private Dental Clinics of Dhaka City

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Abstract

Infection is one of the most vital problems in health care service worldwide. A cross-sectional study was conducted to assess the standard and level of current infection control practice in the Dental clinics in Dhaka city. A total 110 purposively selected respondents participated in this study, most of them were from middle age group. Among them 68% were male and 32% were female. 62% respondents had graduate level education. By length of practice duration 53.6% had 5-10 years experience and 30.0% treat average 5-10 patients daily. Among the total respondents 77% of Dental surgeons were vaccinated against tetanus and hepatitis and 56% of respondents used to wash hands by water with soap. Within the total participating dentists 66% gave the history of habitual wearing of disposable gloves, 70.0% used disposable masks and 26.4% wore disposable clothes. The study also reported that, 44% of respondents usually washed clinical contact surface in the dental operator by disinfectants and 33% of respondents cleaned the operator surfaces after patient's treatment by water and antiseptics. The study revealed that almost all dental surgeons used to use the disposable instruments & accessories in the clinic, 41% clinicians used dettol in the clinic as disinfecting solution and 35.8% respondents sterilized their instruments by autoclave. The research work found that 73.6% respondents mentioned to clean the prosthodontic instruments by detergent wash, 68.2% mentioned to use glass bid sterilizer to sterilize the endodontic instruments and 68% reported about surgical instruments to sterilize by autoclave just after cleaning with detergent wash without using the disinfectant solutions. This study also found that 77.3% disposed the sharp instruments in plastic container, 20.9% maintained color code during disposal of medical wastes and 58.2% respondents used to dispose medical wastes with general wastes. The study revealed that 69.1% cleaned the non patient area by mop and detergent only. According to the agreements of the respondent's 71% reported that very few of the patients complained about secondary infection, 81% gave no history of cross infection after receiving operative procedure. 50.9% respondents mentioned about participation in training session on infection control procedure at least once in their lifetime. Policy on immunization should be developed for Dental health workers and further studies involving larger sample size is recommended.

Key words: Infection control, sterilization, disposable, dental clinics.

Introduction

Infection is one of the most crucial problems in health care service worldwide.

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It constitutes one of the most important causes of morbidity and mortality associated clinical, diagnostic and therapeutic procedures^{1,2} health care workers are at a high risk of needle stick injuries and blood borne pathogens as they perform their clinical activities in hospitals³. The Dental clinic is an environment where disease transmission occurs easily⁴. There is growing concern about the issue of cross-infection in Dental clinics and laboratories, especially after several studies found that transmission of infection to dental laboratory technicians is mainly by contaminated impressions or by improper handling of clinical items after arrival at the Dental laboratory⁵. Potential pathogenic microbiologic cross-contamination from various sources by the way of dental laboratory has been documented. In prosthodontic laboratories, lathes and pumice used for polishing and finishing of prostheses have been described as the greatest sources of contamination⁶. Infection control forms an important part of practice for all health care professions and remains one of the most cost-beneficial medical interventions available. In Dentistry, both patients and health care workers may be exposed to a number of blood borne and upper respiratory tract pathogens through exposure to blood and saliva⁷.

Most studies of Dentists' infection control practices have investigated compliance with specific procedures, such as the use of gloves and masks, eye protection, hepatitis B virus (HBV) vaccination and heat sterilization of dental hand pieces⁸. Exposure to blood through percutaneous injury or by contact to mucous membranes of the eyes, nose or mouth, or by contact with non-intact skin is the primary method in this practice⁹.

Methods and Materials

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Dhaka city among 110 selected Private Dental practitioners during January to April 2013. Data were collected using a interviewer administered semi-structured questionnaire.

Results

Table-1 Distribution of the respondents by age (n=110)

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
< 30 Years	24	21.8
30 - 40 Years	40	36.4
40 - 50 Years	27	24.5
> 50 Years	19	17.3
Total	110	100.0

Table-1 represents the distribution of the respondents by age. Out of 110 Dental Surgeons 24 (21.8%) were in <30 years, 40 (36.4%) were in 30-40 years, 27 (24.5%) were in 40-50 years and 19 (17.3%) were in age > 50 years.

Table-2 Distribution of the respondents by duration of clinical practice (n=110)

Length of Practice	Frequency	Percentage
< 5 Years	10	9.1
5 -10 Years	59	53.6
10 - 15 Years	20	18.2
15 - 20 Years	12	10.9
> 20 Years	9	8.2

Table-2 represents distribution of the respondents by length of clinical practice. Out of 110 Dental Surgeons 10 (9.1%) practiced for < 5 years, 59 (53.6%) for 5-10 years, 20 (18.2%) for 10-15 years, 12 (10.9%) for 15-20 years and 9 (8.2%) for > 20 years.

Table-3 Distribution of the respondents by treating the number of daily patients (n=110)

No. of daily patients	Frequency	Percentage
< 5	8	7.3
5 - 10	33	30.0
10 - 15	24	21.8
15 - 20	23	20.9
> 20	22	20.0

Table-3 represents respondents by treating the number of daily patients. Out of 110 respondents 8 (7.3%) respondents treated < 5 patients, 33 (30%) treated 5-10 patients, 24 (21.8%) treated 10 – 15 patients, 23 (20.9%) treated 15- 20 patients and 22 (20%) respondents treated > 20 patients.

Figure-1 Distribution of the respondents (Dental Surgeons) by having vaccination against Tetanus & Hepatitis (n=110)

Figure-1 represents distribution of the respondents by having vaccination against tetanus & hepatitis. Among the respondents 85 (77%) were completely vaccinated against tetanus & hepatitis and the other 25 (22%) were not vaccinated.

Figure-2 Distribution of the respondents by method of hand washing before patient's examination (n=110)

Figure-2 represents distribution of the respondents by method of hand washing before patient's examination. Table shows that 7 (6%) respondents used water for hand washing, 61 (56%) used water with soap and 42 (38%) used antiseptic for hand washing.

Figure-3 Distribution of the respondents by method of disinfecting the clinical contact surfaces in the Dental operatory (n=110)

Figure-3 Distribution of the respondents on method of disinfecting the clinical contact surfaces in the Dental operatory (n=110). Figure shows that 43 (39%) washed the clinical contact surface by water and detergent, 48 (44%) by disinfectant agent and rest of 19 (17%) used barrier protection.

Figure-4 Distribution of the respondents by method of cleaning the operatory surfaces after patient's treatment (n=110)

Figure-4 represents distribution of the respondents by method of cleaning the operatory surfaces after patient's treatment. Figure shows that 18 (16%) were cleaning the operatory surface by water, 29 (26%) by water and detergent, 35 (33%) by water and antiseptic and 28 (25%) cleaned by disinfectant agent.

Table-4 Distribution of the respondents by the use of disposable instruments & accessories in the clinic (n=110)

Disposable Instrument	Frequency	Percentage
Syringe	72	65.5
Needle	110	100.0
Cartridge	40	36.4
Suction tips	101	91.8
Surgical blades	88	80.0
Reamer/file/broach/bar	20	18.2
Plastic Glass	93	84.5

*Multiple responses

Table-4 represents distribution of the respondents by the use of disposable instruments & accessories in the clinic. Table shows that 72 (65.5%) respondents used disposable syringe, 110 (100.0%) used disposable needle, 40 (36.4%) used disposable cartridge, 101 (91.8%) used disposable suction tips, 20 (18.2%) used disposable reamer/file/broach/bar and 93 (84.5%) used disposable plastic glass.

Figure 5 Distribution of the respondents by the type of disinfectants used (n=110)

Figure-5 represents distribution of the respondents by the type of disinfectants used in the clinic. Figure shows that 22 (20%) respondents used 0.5% chlorine, 46 (41%) dettol, 2 (2%) phenol, 4 (4%) betadine and rest 36 (33%) used gluterdehyde.

Table 5 Distribution of the respondents by the type of sterilization procedure (n=110)

Sterilization procedure	Frequency	Percentage
Autoclave	81	73.6
Hot air oven	16	14.5
Boiling device	55	50.0
Chemical	74	67.3

*Multiple responses

Table-5 represents distribution of the respondents by the use of sterilization procedure in their clinic. Table shows that 81 (73.6%) respondents were sterilized the instruments by autoclave, 16 (14.5%) by hot air oven, 55 (50.0%) by boiling device and 74 (67.3%) by chemical method.

Table-6 Distribution of the respondents by methods of disinfection of endodontic instruments (n=110)

Disinfect the endodontic instrument	Frequency	Percentage
Detergent wash	82	74.5
Autoclave	24	21.8
Hot air oven	7	6.4
Ultraviolet ray	10	9.1
Boiling	25	22.7
Glass bid sterilizer	75	68.2

* Multiple responses

Table-6 Distribution of the respondents by methods of disinfection of endodontic instruments. Table shows that 82 (74.5%) respondents were disinfect the endodontic instruments by detergent wash, 24 (21.8%) by autoclave, 7 (6.4%) by hot air oven, 10 (9.1%) by ultraviolet ray, 25 (22.7%) by boiling and 75 (68.2%) by glass bid sterilizer.

Table-7 Distribution of the respondents by methods of disinfection of prosthodontic instruments (n=110)

Disinfect the prosthodontic instrument	Frequency	Percentage
Detergent wash	81	73.6
Autoclave	14	12.7
Hot air oven	2	1.9
Ultraviolet ray	1	0.9
Boiling	12	10.9

Table-7 Distribution of the respondents on methods of disinfection of prosthodontic instruments. Table shows that 81 (73.6%) were disinfected the prosthodontic instrument by detergent wash, 14 (12.7%) by autoclave, 2 (1.8%) by hot air oven, 1 (0.9%) by ultraviolet ray and 12 (10.9%) were disinfected by boiling method.

Figure-6 Distribution of the respondents by types of water used during Dental treatment (n=110)

Figure-6 represents distribution of the respondents by types of water used during dental treatment. Above the figure shows that 77 (70.0%) used supply water, 6 (5%), boiled water, 25 (23%) filter water, and only 2 (2%) respondent used distilled water during treatment procedure.

Table-8 Distribution of the respondents by the way of disposal of sharp instruments (n=110)

Dispose of sharp waste	Frequency	Percentage
Glass container	8	7.3
Metal container	2	1.8
Plastic container	85	77.3
with other wastes together in any container	15	13.6

Table-8 represents distribution of the respondents by the way of disposal of sharp instruments. Out of 110 respondents, 8 (7.3%) disposed the sharp instrument in glass container, 2 (1.8%) in metal container, 85 (77.3%) in plastic container and 15 (13.6%) disposed the sharp instruments with other wastes together in any container.

Table-9 Distribution of respondents by the methods of cleaning the non patient area (n=110)

Clinic clean the non patient area	Frequency	Percentage
Mop and detergent only	76	69.1
Mop with detergent when visibly solid	14	12.7
Mop with disinfectant	20	18.2

Table-9 represents distribution of the respondents by the methods of cleaning the non patient area. Out of 110 respondents 76 (69.1%) used mope and detergent only, 14 (12.7%) used mop with detergent when visibly solid and 20 (18.2%) used mop with disinfectant solution.

Discussion

This cross-sectional study was carried out to assess the infection control measures among 110 selected private dental practitioners at Dhaka City of Bangladesh. Among the respondents one-fifth were in age group of <30 years, one-third were in age group of 30-40 years, one-fourth were in age group of 40-50 years and around twenty percent were in age group of >50 years (mean±SD 41.25±11.953 years). Among all near about seventy percent were male. By level of education one fourth had diploma level education; sixty percent had completed graduation level. The current study revealed that among the total respondents near about ten percent were involved in this profession for less than 5 years, above half of them for 5-10 years, around one fifth for 10-15 years, ten percent for 15-20 years and less than ten percent for above 20 years (mean 2.55±1.072 years). Availability of patients to most of the doctors was on average 5-10 in number per day. According to the results of present study above seventy percent of Dental Surgeons were vaccinated against tetanus and hepatitis. A survey of U.S. Dental laboratories reported that 56.4% of Dental assistants were vaccinated against hepatitis B.⁶ One more study carried out by Maupome et al in Mexico City reported that 67.1% of dental personnel were immunized against hepatitis. Six percent of the respondents used to wash their hands before examining the patients by water, above half of them washed their hands by water and soap together and one-third used antiseptic during hand washing. The most important techniques of "universal precaution" are barrier techniques which include wearing gloves, protective clothing, masks and protective eye wear. Disposable gloves must be worn even when examining the patients. The present study shows that the practice of wearing disposable gloves was above 60%, disposable masks 70%, and one-fourth wearing disposable clothes. The study exposes that above 60% of respondents' the assistants used PPE and around 67% respondents' assistants used gloves during cleaning and disinfecting procedures. The study carried out by Razak et al (1995) in Malaysia concluded that 54.0% of the respondents routinely wear gloves and about 83.0% of dentists wear mask. South African Dentists used gloves by 87.0%. Aziawa et al (1996) stated that gloves and other protective garments were generally worn.^{11,12,13,14} Among the respondents dealing with clinical contact surface in the Dental operatory, above forty percent used to wash with water and detergent, less than 45% used disinfectant agent and below 20% used barrier protection.

In case of the use of variety of disinfectants in the clinics it is observed that one-fifth used 0.5% chlorine, 41% used dettol, 2% used phenol, and 4% used betadine and above one-third used gluteraldehyde. To perform the sterilization of instruments in the dental clinic above one-third used autoclave. Dealing with the sterilization of endodontic instruments this study shows that above 35% respondents used detergent wash, above 10% used autoclave and above 30% used to use glass bid sterilizer. On the other hand for prosthodontic instruments more than 70% participants agreed to use detergent wash, more than 10% used autoclave and also more than 10% used boiling device. Surgical instruments intended for sterilization and disinfections must be done carefully. Among the respondents below 70% gave the history of cleaning their instruments firstly by water and detergent and secondly using the autoclave. School of Dentistry, Virginia, USA, expressed their faculty practice as instrument preparation includes ultrasonic cleaning in a bacterium cleaning solution. This study revealed that water and soap was the most common antiseptic solution for cleaning the instruments. No other significant study was observed between degree and cleaning practice of instruments.¹¹⁻¹⁵ About the types of water used in the Dental clinics during treatment it is observed here that 70% participants used supply water. Among the dental professionals as a matter of disposal of sharp instruments we get the data of 8% using glass container, 2% using metal container, above 70% using plastic container and below 15% disposing the sharp instruments with other wastes together in any container. The study revealed that non patient area in the clinics were cleaned with mop and detergent only by around 70% and around 20% used mop with disinfectant.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Infection control is a burning topic in health care, especially in Dentistry. Dental staff should have most up to date knowledge about the procedures required to prevent the transmission of infection. Among the respondents majority were male and graduate, and half of respondents were practicing for 5-10 years. Among the respondents eighty percent were completely vaccinated against tetanus and hepatitis. The current study revealed that among the respondents above seventy percent used disposable gloves and protective eye wear and seventy percent used disposable masks during practice. On the basis of findings of the study following recommendations may be made, the Ministry of Health has to provide formal intensive training courses on infection control for the Dental professionals of all categories

Before issuing license to the Dental clinics special attention needs to be given on the infection control status of the clinic, policies and programs should be developed and implemented for Dental health workers in respect of training, education and self immunization, further studies on the topic involving larger sample size are needed.

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Oral Effects of Renal Disease: A Medical Problem in Dentistry

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Abstract

The number of patients with chronic kidney disease especially with diabetic nephropathy is expected to grow significantly in the future. It is associated with substantial morbidity and mortality, and the consequence of this emerging public health problem is considerable consumption of medical and financial resources. Thereby, there is a higher chance to see such patients in a dental office. People with kidney disease and those on dialysis are more likely to have periodontal disease and other oral health problems than the general population. Build up of bacteria in the mouth can cause infection. Because people with kidney disease have weakened immune systems, they are more susceptible to infections. Moreover, bone loss in the jaw can occur in those with kidney disease. Calcium imbalance contributes to loss of calcium from the bones resulting in weak bones. Weak bones can cause teeth to become loose and potentially fall out. The doctor may recommend antibiotics be taken prior to the dental procedure to help guard against infection. The purpose of this article is to evaluate oral and dental manifestations in patients on haemodialysis and kidney transplant recipients, and understanding the use and adjustment of common dental drugs which aid clinicians in safely treating these patients as well as to clarify the possible basic role in managing renal disease patients.

Key words: Kidney disease, dental drugs, oral manifestation, renal nutrition, transplantation.

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease is defined by the presence of a marker of kidney damage, such as proteinuria (ratio of greater than 30 mg of albumin to 1 g of creatinine on

untimed [spot] urine testing), or a decreased glomerular filtration rate (GFR < 60 mL per minute per 1.73 m²) for three or more months.¹ Estimates of the global burden of disease indicate that diseases of the kidney and urinary tract account for approximately 830,000 deaths and 18,467,000 disability-adjusted life years annually, ranking them 12th among causes of death (1.4 percent of all deaths) and 17th among causes of disability (1.0 percent of all disability-adjusted life years).² In the United States, kidney failure is becoming increasingly common and is associated with poor health outcomes and high medical expenditures. In 2009, 116,395 patients started therapy for end-stage renal disease (ESRD), and the prevalent population reached 571,414 (including 398,861 dialysis patients); 17,736 transplants were performed, and 172,553 patients had a functioning graft at year's end.³

There is about 5% annual increase in the number of patients with chronic kidney failure, patients undergoing haemodialysis or kidney transplantation.⁴ Around 20 million (two crore) people have been suffering from kidney diseases, especially chronic kidney disease (CKD) in Bangladesh. Kidney diseases claim at least five lives every hour and over 40,000 lives a year. Nearly 85 percent of the patients do not realize they are affected by kidney diseases before going for treatment.⁵ Although national registries are not available, the data from different medical colleges and community based studies in this country suggest that glomerulonephritis, acute and chronic renal failure, urinary tract infection, renal stone diseases and obstructive uropathy are common renal problems.⁶

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Improper kidney function is reflected in every organ system of body, showing various signs and symptoms. About 90% of renal failure patients have oral symptoms.⁷ Diabetes mellitus is the most frequent cause of ESRD. Type 2 diabetes mellitus accounts for about two thirds of diabetes-related cases. Hypertension is the second most frequent cause of ESRD. Renal arterial diseases-including both large and small vessel disease-appear to be raising incidence, especially in the elder. The causes of chronic renal failure (CRF) are similar to those for ESRD.⁸ Renal disease has become important in dentistry because of the growing number of patients who, as a result of renal dialysis or transplantation, survive renal failure. Aspects of renal disease affecting dental management are: Heparinisation before dialysis, Possible hepatitis B or C carriage after chronic dialysis, Permanent venous fistulae susceptible to infection, Secondary hyperparathyroidism, Immunosuppressive treatment for nephritic syndrome or transplant patients, Oral lesions due to drugs, particularly for immunosuppression, Low doses or withholding of many drugs: e.g. some cephalosporins and tetracyclines, and Oral lesions of chronic renal failure.⁹

A new study has revealed that patients suffering from end-stage renal failure (ESRF) and those receiving dialysis are more prone to periodontal disease and other oral health problems. The renal failure groups had higher gingival index (GI) and bleeding, probing depths, attachment loss, hypoplasia and obliteration and less caries, than the control. Plaque was higher in the dialysis and pre-dialysis (PD) groups. Dialysis duration and end-stage renal failure significantly correlated with gingivitis, probing depth, attachment loss and enamel hypoplasia.¹⁰ Several studies have demonstrated higher rates of oral pathology in dialysis patients with one or more oral symptoms such as xerostomia, taste disturbances, uremic odor, tongue coating, mucosal inflammation, mucosal petechia/ecchymosis, oral ulceration, or enamel hypoplasia. Xerostomia (or dryness of the mouth) may predispose to caries and gingival inflammation as well as contribute to difficulties with speech, denture retention, mastication, dysphagia, sore mouth, loss of taste, and infections.¹¹

Oral and dental manifestation

Xerostomia: The main oral health problem experienced by renal patients is xerostomia.

This is as a result of several factors which include multiple medication, restricted intake of fluids and diabetes in which many renal patients suffer from. Xerostomia may also predispose the patient to caries, mucositis and oral infection as the protective factors in saliva are not present. For the HD and immunosuppressed transplant patient infections in the oral cavity may act as foci in other sites of the body.¹²

Bad odor (secondary to uremia) and metallic taste:

People with renal problems may have a bad taste and odor in their mouths, which occurs because the kidneys are not removing urea from the blood resulting from the increased concentration of urea in saliva and the urea is breaking down to form ammonia.¹³

Plaque and calculus: Dialysis patients may form calculus more rapidly than healthy individuals possibly due to high salivary urea and phosphate levels.¹⁴ A significant correlation between plaque scores and gingival inflammation in renal dialysis patients has also been reported.^{15, 16}

Stomatitis: In kidney failure, blood urea level increases which results in uremic stomatitis. Uremic stomatitis in the following two forms: Erythromultaceous form characterized by red mucosa covered with thick exudates and pseudomembrane and Ulcerative form characterized by ulcerations with redness and pultaceous (pulpy) coating.¹⁷

Gingival hyperplasia: One of the most typical findings in patients with endstage renal failure is gingival hyperplasia (drug induced gingival overgrowth), which mechanism of occurrence is multifactorial and still unknown. Taking antihypertensive drugs (calcium channel blocker) and immunosuppressive drugs give its impact in the oral cavity. Such gingival expansion occurred more frequently in the early post-transplant period (4 months) and in combination with low oral hygiene.¹⁸

Hairy leukoplakia: Oral hairy leukoplakia (OHL) is associated to the Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), and different studies suggest that primary infection occurs in the oropharynx, where the virus remains latent in the basal layers of the epithelium until reactivation takes place as a result of immune depression - with the generation of tongue lesions.¹⁹

Enamel hypoplasia: Children with renal failure may have enamel hypoplasia and dysplastic dentine with delayed eruption of teeth.⁹

Jaw bone alteration: Other oral manifestations of renal disease are related to renal osteodystrophy (RO), a common condition which is considered as a dysfunctional mineral homeostasis. These manifestations appear in late stage. Disorders in calcium and phosphorus metabolism, abnormal vitamin D metabolism and increased compensatory parathyroid activity are the main causes. Secondary hyperparathyroidism develops when the kidney secretes more phosphate ions and also osteoblastic and osteoclastic activity increases. Cortical expansion and gingival swelling originated from giant cell lesions may occur.²⁰ The oral manifestations of hyperparathyroidism appears frequently in the mandibular molar region these changes are: Total or partial loss of lamina dura, Bone demineralization, Loss of trabeculation, Giant cell tumors, Tooth mobility, Malocclusion, Metastatic soft tissue calcifications, and The teeth may be painful on percussion and mastication. Malocclusion is due to increased mobility and drifting of teeth and demineralization of temporomandibular and paratemporomandibular bones.¹⁷

Erosions: Severe erosions on the lingual surfaces of the teeth, due to frequent regurgitation and vomiting induced by uremia and medication, and nausea associated to dialysis.²¹

Malignization: Normal renal function and health can be restored by transplantation, but it is associated with the complications of prolonged immunosuppressive treatment, particularly susceptibility to infections or lymphomas.⁹

Oral and dental management

End stage renal failure is a life threatening condition. The kidneys regulate fluids, excrete nitrogenous waste, synthesize vitamin D and erythropoietin (EPO), maintain acid-base homeostasis regulate mineral and electrolyte balance and regulate the metabolism and excretion of drugs. All of these things can affect dental treatment due to the resulting abnormalities. Dialysis patients are heparinized and so in order to avoid abnormal bleeding tendencies, treatment should be carried out the day after dialysis. The patient has the maximum benefit from the dialysis and the effect of the heparin has worn off. For the transplant patient only emergency treatment should be carried out within the first three months after transplantation. It is also suggested that transplant recipients should receive antibiotic prophylaxis prior to dental treatment.²²

Dental drugs

Drugs that are directly nephrotoxic must be avoided. Drugs excreted mainly by the kidney may have undesirably enhanced or prolonged activity if doses are not lowered. Drug therapy may need to be adjusted, depending on the degree of renal failure, the patient's dialysis schedule, or the presence of a transplant. Except in emergency, such drugs should be prescribed only after consultation with the renal physician.²³

Antibiotics: Renal disease also has significant effect on antimicrobials. Because dosage adjust is required for most antimicrobials, it is of practical value for the clinicians to be familiar with the oral antibiotics that do not need dosage reductions. Penicillins not requiring dosage adjustment in case of moderate renal insufficiency include dicloxacillin, nafcillin and penicillin VK. Penicillins have a wide therapeutic margin of safety but are neurotoxic at high dosages and seizures can occur. Of the oral cephalosporins, only cefuroxime axetil needs no dosage adjustment. Macrolides not requiring adjustment include erythromycin and azithromycin. Doxycycline and minocycline are excreted via the biliary route, do not accumulate, do not aggravate uremia and, thus, do not need dosage adjustment. Clindamycin is the other commonly used dental oral antibiotic not needing dosage adjustment. Once a patient's Glomerular filtration rate (GFR) declines to less than 50 mL/minute, most other antibiotics require dosage or dosing interval adjustment.²⁴

Fluorides: Fluoride can usually safely be given topically for caries prophylaxis. Systemic fluorides should not be given, because of doubt about fluoride excretion by damaged kidneys.²³ For patients receiving haemodialysis (HD) and continuous ambulatory peritoneal dialysis (CAPD), serum fluoride accumulation is a risk factor.²⁵ Persistent high levels of plasma fluoride in such patients can cause osteodystrophy and other done damage.²⁶ If fluoridated community water is used to mix the dialysates, it may lead to fluoride toxicity, fluorosis and renal osteodystrophy. So dialysis patient should receive dialysates that are mixed with purified and de-ionized water.¹⁷

Immunosuppressives: In general, kidney transplants involve the risk of transplanted organ rejection. In order to prevent this, patients who have undergone an organ transplant operation, are given huge doses of immunosuppressants such as corticosteroids, azathioprin,

cyclosporine and anti-lymphocyte globulin. Accordingly, in patients who underwent kidney transplant operations prophylactic antibiotics should be administered in consultation with the patient's physician. Because of potential adrenalin crisis risk, it is necessary to alter steroid therapy. If the stress suffered during the oral surgical intervention is minimal, the therapy should be altered. If the stress is insignificant, it is recommended to increase the steroid dosage twice a day two days prior and following the oral surgical intervention. If the stress is great, 100g of hydrocortisone should be administered i.m. prior to the operation, gradually reducing dosage by 50% on a daily basis for three days after the intervention until the dosage of 20mg which should be administered twice a day for the subsequent 7 days. In any case, steroid dosage is administered by the expert physician after consultations with the dentist and the expert stress assessment.²⁷

Analgesic: aspirin and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDS) should be avoided since they aggravate gastrointestinal irritation and bleeding associated with chronic renal failure (CRF). Their excretion may also be delayed and they may be nephrotoxic, especially in the elderly or where there is renal damage or cardiac failure. Some patients have peptic ulceration, which is a further contraindication to aspirin. Even COX-2 inhibitors may be nephrotoxic and are best avoided.²³ For mild pain, acetaminophen is the analgesic of choice and is safe in chronic kidney disease (CKD). It is extensively metabolized by the liver with less than 5% excreted unchanged via kidney. For moderate pain, and pain inadequately controlled acetaminophen, weak opioids should be considered. For patients with severe pain or on-going moderate pain despite weak opioids, strong opioids are recommended. Those believed most efficacious and safe in CKD patients are hydromorphone, methadone, and fentanyl.²⁸ Tapentadol has recently been introduced into clinical and has been approved by the FDA for moderate to severe pain, and the potency is said to be somewhere between morphine and tramadol. It does not appear to cause the confusional states sometimes associated with tramadol. In various studies, tapentadol has been found to be effective even for severe postoperative pain.⁶ There is every possibility that tapentadol may improve upon the analgesic safety of morphine and tramadol while reducing the incidence of side-effects, if used appropriately.²⁹

Local Anaesthesia and conscious sedation: Local anaesthesia is safe unless there is a severe bleeding tendency. Relative analgesia (conscious sedation) may be used. The veins of the forearms and the saphenous veins are lifelines for patients on regular haemodialysis. If it is necessary to give intravenous sedation, or take blood, other veins such as those at or above the elbow should be used because of the risk of consequent fistula infection or thrombophlebitis. Midazolam is preferable to diazepam because of the lower risk of thrombophlebitis.²³

General anaesthetics: Patients with chronic renal disease (CRD) have multiple general anaesthesia (GA) risk factors.³⁰ General anaesthetics pose specific problems for renal patients as they are highly sensitive to the myocardial depressant effects. Myocardial depression and dysrhythmias are especially likely in poorly controlled metabolic acidosis.²³ Chronic anaemia is common in patients with CRF who are not being treated with erythropoietin and is usually well tolerated. Unless the patient has ischaemic heart disease the haemoglobin level may be maintained at around 7-8 g/dl. Uraemic patients may have a bleeding tendency due to a decrease in platelet adhesion and fragility of the vessel walls.³¹ However there is no evidence that GA presents a higher risk than other techniques. In general, there is a lack of research comparing outcomes from different anaesthetic methods. In one retrospective study there was no increase in mortality, cardiac morbidity or fistula failure in patients undergoing procedures under general anaesthesia compared to local anaesthesia (LA) infiltration or regional anaesthesia (RA) brachial plexus block, although the comparison was underpowered. Patients often have an expectation of general anaesthesia when presenting for surgery. With careful planning they can be offered GA with minimal increased risk.³⁰

Anti-fungal: For mucocutaneous candida infection, topical therapy with clotrimazole or nystatin is usually effective, but if this fails fluconazole therapy is suggested. In general, mucocutaneous overgrowth can be prevented by treatment of high-risk patients (those receiving antibiotic therapy, or high-dose immunosuppression) with nystatin oral washes. For life-threatening infection, Amphotericin B is probably more effective because it controls the infection sooner, although fluconazole is less toxic.

Fluconazole increases cyclosporine levels and therefore cyclosporine levels must be frequently checked when patient is on fluconazole. Liposome Amphotericin has been used instead of Amphotericin B because there is less nephrotoxicity with similar efficacy; however, it is very expensive.³²

Adjuvant and other drugs: Adjuvant drugs refer to medications with a primary indication other than pain that possess analgesic potential. It can also refer to agents that minimize concomitant psychological disturbances such as insomnia, depression, or anxiety and drugs used to treat adverse effects of analgesics such as anti-emetics, laxatives, and psychotropics.²⁷ Monoamine oxidase inhibitors (MAOIs) can cause severe reaction with opioids. The onset can be very sudden and, with pathedine, can be fatal.³³ The World Health Organization (WHO) has devised a “ladder” system to help structure initial and adjuvant analgesic medication choice (Table 1).³⁴ Antacids containing magnesium salts should not be given as there may be magnesium retention. Antacids containing calcium or aluminium bases may impair absorption of penicillin V and sulphonamides. Cholestyramine, sometimes used in CRF, may also interfere with the absorption of penicillins.²³ Patients with CKD often develop iron deficiency anaemia and require oral iron supplements or intravenous supplementation with iron dextrans, ferric gluconate, iron sucrose or ferumoxytol in addition to erythropoietin injections.³⁵ Table 2 shows dose adjustment of some of the most used drugs in dentistry, depending on creatinine clearance.³⁶

<p>Step 1: Mild pain (rating of 1-4 on 0-10 scale) Non-narcotic analgesics (eg. acetylsalicylic acid, acetaminophen, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs) ± Adjuvant therapy</p>
<p>Step 2: Mild to moderate pain (rating of 5-6 on 0-10 scale) Opioids (eg. codeine, oxycodone, hydrocodone, tramadol) ± Nonopioid ± Adjuvant therapy</p>
<p>Step 3: Moderate to severe pain (rating of 7-10 on 0-10 scale) Opioids (eg. Morphine, hydromorphone, methadone, fentanyl, oxycodone) ± Nonopioid ± Adjuvant therapy</p>
<p>*Medications to counteract opioid side effects or provide additional analgesia (eg. Anticonvulsants, antiepileptics, corticosteroids, and/or step 1 medications).</p>

DRUGS	DOSE ADJUSTMENT ACCORDING TO CREATININE CLEARANCE		
	Normal dose	Dose with CC 10-50 ml/min	Dose with CC <10 ml/min
ANTIBIOTIC			
Amoxicillin	500/ 1000 mg/ 8 h	500/ 1000 mg/ 8-12 h	500/ 1000 mg/ 12- 24 h
Amoxicillin/clavulanate	500/ 875 mg/ 8 h	No need for dose adjustment	500/ 875 mg/ 12- 24 h
Penicillin G	0.3-1.2 million IU/ 6-12 h	50-100% of the dose every 8- 12 h	25-50% of the dose every 12 h
Clindamycin	300 mg/ 8 h	No need for dose adjustment	No need for dose adjustment
Doxycyclin	100 mg/ 24 h	No need for dose adjustment	No need for dose adjustment

Erythromycin	250-500 mg/ 6 h	No need for dose adjustment	No need for dose adjustment
Metronidazole	250-500 mg/ 6 h	Every 8-12 h	Every 12-14 h
Azithromycin,	500 mg/ 24 h, 3 days	No need for dose adjustment	No need for dose adjustment
ANTIFUNGAL			
Anfotericin	0.3-1 mg/kg/ 24 h	No need for dose adjustment	0.3-1 mg/ kg/ 24-48 h
Fluconazol	100-200 mg/ 24 h	50-200 every 24 h	50-100 every 24 h
ANALGESIC			
Paracetamol	500-1000 mg/4-6 h	No need for dose adjustment	No need for dose adjustment
Aspirin	Contraindicated (produces water retention, deterioration of renal function and risk of gastric hemorrhage)		
Ibuprofen	200-600 mg/4-6 h	No need for dose adjustment	No need for dose adjustment
Dihydrocodeine	10-30 mg/ 4-6 h	Decrease dose 25%	Decrease dose 25%
CC: Creatinine clearance Table 2. Dose adjustment according to creatinine clearance of the drugs more frequently prescribed in dentistry.			

Renal nutrition management

Diet counseling by a renal disease needs to be individualized based on many factors including: kidney function, lifestyle, culture, religion, financial status, other co-morbid conditions, treatment goals and biochemical parameters. The diet may have to be modified for sodium, protein, potassium and/or phosphorus.³⁷

Dietary protein: The benefits of dietary protein restriction for patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) were established over 100 years ago. In 1869, Beale and colleagues showed that the uraemic symptoms in patients with kidney failure were ameliorated by reducing foods rich in protein. The benefits of dietary protein restriction are multifactorial. First, restricting protein in the diet provides favourable metabolic parameters. The typical biochemical profile (acidaemia, hyperphosphataemia, azotaemia) seen in CKD patients who receive minimal attention to their diet is not typically seen when proper dietary counseling is emphasised. Moreover, dietary protein restriction has been shown to improve insulin resistance and osteodystrophy. Patients with CKD (with an average GFR of 18ml/min) were given a protein-restrictive diet along with amino acid analogue supplements, and were found to maintain a neutral nitrogen balance without the development of acidaemia or hyperphosphataemia.³⁸

Low-Phosphorus diet: The dietary phosphorus is mainly derived from 2 sources: dietary proteins and phosphorus additives. These additives are an important component of processed foods such as meats, cheeses, dressings, beverages, and bakery products.

They can increase the dietary phosphorus intake by as much as 1 g/day. Nutrient composition tables usually do not include the phosphorus additives, which results in underestimation of phosphorus intake. Moreover, the phosphorus derived from plants is in the form of phytate and is less absorbable by the human intestines because of a lack of the enzyme phytase. In a study of 29,076 patients on haemodialysis, Shinaberger et al demonstrated that a high-protein/low-phosphorus diet is associated with the best survival, and the highest mortality rate was found in patients on low-protein/low-phosphorus diet.³⁹

Phosphate binders: Phosphate binders are the mainstay of therapy for secondary hyperparathyroidism. The noncompliance to dietary restriction as well as the need to ensure adequate protein intake often result in the addition of phosphate binders to limit the net absorption of dietary phosphorus. In a recent study published in December 2008, patients treated with phosphate binders during the first 90 days after starting dialysis had a 30% lower risk of death compared with those who were not treated. Several modalities have been tried, including aluminum hydroxide, calcium salts, sevelamer hydrochloride (Renagel, Genzyme Corp., Cambridge, MA) and lanthanum carbonate (Fosrenol, Shire US, Inc., Wayne, PA).⁴⁰

Vitamin D and its derivatives: Vitamin D is one of the oldest treatments for secondary hyperparathyroidism. It is known that calcitriol deficiency and resistance are major contributors to the pathophysiology of the disease and that calcitriol supplementation is effective in suppressing high levels of PTH. On the other hand, calcitriol enhances the intestinal absorption of calcium and phosphorus, increasing their blood levels and possibly increasing their product.⁴¹ The second-generation agents (Selective Vitamin D Analogues) cause less hypercalcemia and hyperphosphatemia than traditional calcitriol. Two agents are available and widely used in the United States: paricalcitol (Zemplar, Abbott Laboratories, Abbott Park, IL) and doxercalciferol (Hectorol, Genzyme Corp.).⁴²

Sodium: The importance of salt restriction in the treatment of patients with renal disease has remained highly controversial. In patients with chronic kidney disease a high salt intake may be “nephrotoxic” by indirect mechanisms, e.g. by an increase in blood pressure and by attenuation of the pharmacologic blockade of the renin–angiotensin system blunting its anti-hypertensive and anti-proteinuric effect.

The sodium content of most commercially available food items is too high, and this accounts for nearly three-quarters of salt intake. There is strong evidence that salt intake plays an important role in the genesis of hypertension and target organ damage. Both high and low sodium intake cause adverse effects. The average salt intake of healthy children and adults exceeds, by far, the recommendations of current guidelines.⁴³

Conclusion

The balance of blood chemistry is fundamentally affected by nutrition and the dietary intake of specific nutrients. The management of the renal patient, therefore, includes not only dose adjustment and restriction of drugs but dietary restriction and regulation as well, which may contribute to anxiety and aversion to further preventive instruction. In addition to good oral health promotion, there is an increased need for collaboration between the dental and medical professions to provide safe and appropriate dental care for these patients.

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Median rhomboid glossitis with palatal 'kissing lesion' – A case report

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Abstract

Median rhomboid glossitis manifests as a well-delineated erythematous area located along the midline posterior dorsal tongue. Its rhomboid shape usually "points" in an antero-posterior direction. Median rhomboid glossitis may have a "kissing lesion," or area of roughness, most commonly in the area of the hard and soft palate. Here is a case report of 24 year old male patient having median rhomboid glossitis with kissing lesions over the hard palate.

Key words: Median rhomboid glossitis, candidiasis, kissing lesion.

Introduction

Anomalies resulting from disturbances of growth and development can be referred to as developmental malformations. These may be congenital – a congenital disease being one which is present before or at birth. Congenital anomalies or diseases may be inherited, i.e. transmitted through genes, but many are not hereditary.¹ These types of defects are often major patient complaints and cause confusion among clinicians. These conditions may cause some difficulties in establishing a definitive diagnosis and appropriate management.

This dilemma not only causes some concern to the patients because of thoughts regarding infection, transmission, and malignancy but it can complicate both the use of clinical or laboratory tests and patient orientation and treatment. Because of patient concern and sometimes symptoms, it is always important to be able to assure patients that these conditions are neither precancerous nor contagious. The basic explanation of these developmental and acquired conditions is best characterized as manifestations (phenotypic expression) of subtle and unidentified genetic defects, probably at specific chromosomal loci. Median rhomboid glossitis (MRG) is thought to be a congenital abnormality related to the persistence of an embryonic midline tongue structure, the tubercular impar.²

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Glossite lasangigue mediane de la face dorsal langue was the name given initially by Brocq and Pautrier to a benign lesion which occurs in posterior midline of the dorsum of the tongue at about the middle third or in front of circumvallate papillae.³

Median rhomboid glossitis (MRG) also known under the terms, Central papillary atrophy of the tongue (CPA), localized atrophy of the tongue papillae (LAT), atrophy of the tongue papillae, median type (ATP) is a benign lesion of uncertain etiology. This lesion used to be considered solely as a developmental disorder.⁴

Median rhomboid glossitis (MRG) is characterized by a shiny oval or diamond-shaped depapillated region on the dorsal midline of the tongue just anterior to the circumvallate papillae. The specific location suggests a developmental anomaly related to persistence of an embryonic structure, 'tuberculum impar'. However, the lesion is now believed to be a localized chronic infection by *Candida albicans*. Sometimes, MRG occurs in association with candidal commissural leukoplakias and palatine kissing lesions. The estimated prevalence of MRG among adults is less than 1%.⁵

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Case Report

A 24-year-old male patient reported with chief complaint of redness over the tongue since 6 to 7 years. Patient gave history of erythematous lesion on the dorsal surface of tongue 7 years back with no increase in size, patient has also history of burning sensation over the posterior region of palate while taking the spicy food. Patient had history of chewing pan masala with tobacco since three years 3-4 pouches per day. There was no relevant family history as well as no known history of allergies and medication. On examination patient was moderately built and nourished and his vital signs were within normal limit.

Intraoral examination revealed sharply demarcated, slightly elevated, red, depapillated, rhomboid lesion approximate 2x1cms in size present on the dorsal surface of the tongue on midline just one cm anterior to the circumvallate papillae. (Fig.1) On palpation the lesion was non tender, non-fluctuant and firm in consistency. 4 to 5 erythematous lesions approximate 3x4 mm in size with ill define margins were present over the posterior part of the hard palate just opposite to the rhomboid lesion present on the dorsal surface of the tongue. Lesions were non tender on palpation, soft in consistency and no bleeding was present. (Fig.2) There was generalized edema of gingiva with bleeding on probing and deposits of stains and calculus. Based on history and clinical examination, a provisional diagnosis of median rhomboid glossitis was given, as this entity was concomitant with palatal inflammation so provisional diagnosis of kissing lesions was given for palatal lesions. Patient was checked for HIV by the Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) which was found to be non reactive. Tongue and palate culture was done by the scraping on the lesion and swab was transferred into one ml sterile phosphate-buffered saline solution and inoculated on Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) supplemented with 1% chloramphenicol. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. Grams stained smear show dark haematoxyphilyc round to oval budding form suggestive of *Candida*.

Fig. 1 Sharply demarcated, slightly elevated, red, depapillated, rhomboid lesion

Fig. 2: Erythematous lesions over the posterior part of the hard palate.

(Fig.3 & Fig.4) Capsule Canditral (Itraconazole 100 mg) once daily for 15 days with topical application of lotion Candid -B (Clotrimazole 1%, Beclomethasone dipropionate 0.025%) for 15 days was prescribed. The patient was advised to maintain proper oral hygiene. After two week follow up patient got relive in symptoms.

Fig. 3: Dark haematoxyphilyc round to oval budding form of *Candida* from tongue lesion

Fig. 4: Dark haematoxyphilyc round to oval budding form of *Candida* from palatal lesions.

Discussion

Median rhomboid glossitis is a benign tumor of the tongue often erroneously mistaken for cancer. It is described as a roughly rhomboid shaped mass, situated in the midline of the dorsum of the tongue, usually about one cm. anterior to the circumvallate papillae. It may be smooth, shiny, red and studded with yellow spots, or composed of closely grouped, wart-like nodules with shallow fissures between them.⁶ Median rhomboid glossitis (MRG), first described by Brocq in 1914, occurs in less than 1% of the general population.⁷ The prevalence of median rhomboid glossitis in general population is less than 1% and in Indian population varies between 0.04 and 0.01% with adult males being more commonly affected than females.³

MRG is classically described as a focus of symmetrical filiform papillary atrophy and may exhibit either a smooth or a lobulated surface architecture.⁸ The most common clinical presentation of the disease is an erythematous or white- erythematous area on the dorsal median surface of the tongue, immediately prior to Region V of the circumvallate papilla (terminal gingiva). The erythematous region of the mucosa can be flat or raised. It is normally well circumscribed, with a rhomboid shape, and smooth.⁹ Its aetiology is unknown, although it has been proposed that it may be derived from chronic candidiasis, or that it may be of embryological, inflammatory, or even immunological origin. Reported associated factors include smoking, diabetes mellitus dental prostheses, small traumas and candidal infections.^{3,10,11}

Strong association between localized atrophy of tongue (LAT) and tobacco smoking has been suggested by studies done in India.

Mehta *et al* in 1971 conducted a random sample of 10000 villagers in Ernakulam district, Kerala, India, the prevalence of localized atrophy of tongue (LAT) was 2.3% among bidi smokers, 1.3% among cigarette smokers and 0.5% among non-smokers.⁴ It has been thought that MRG was a developmental anomaly generated by failure of the tuberculum impar to withdraw before fusion of the lateral halves of the tongue, with subsequent failure of the filiform papillae to develop in the mid-dorsal tongue. However, MRG has not been reported in a child. Therefore, this lesion is now believed to be related to a chronic infection by *Candida albicans*.⁵ Recent theories suggest the role of *Candida albicans* – a type of yeast, which causes fungal infection. Hence it can be said to be a type of Candidiasis, which may lead to excessive surface keratin. By studying the biopsies of some patients with MRG in 1975, Cooke discovered that *Candida* caused mucosa colonization on the tongue. This infection may be caused along with secondary hyperplasia. MRG is mostly asymptomatic. In some patients, however, general discomfort can be sensed – especially in the site which is evident of atrophic changes. Itching or burning sensation can be caused in the dorsal line of the tongue but it is not painful. Even in such cases, symptoms seem to be transitory.¹²

Sometimes a “kissing” lesion develops on the palate, directly opposite from the tongue lesion. This is more common in people whose immune system is suppressed and is believed to result from the fungal organisms on the top of tongue being transferred to the palate during swallowing and similar movements.¹³ When Median rhomboid glossitis is found in association with palatal inflammation corresponding to contact with the involved area on the tongue immunosuppression should be rule out in those patient. In present case *Candida* species of both lesions (median rhomboid glossitis and kissing lesions of hard palate) were the same. This finding suggests that these lesions may be due to prolonged contact between the *Candida*-infected midline dorsum of the tongue and the hard palate.¹³

Diagnosis of MRG is basically clinical, although sometimes histopathology is required for differential diagnosis. Though the diagnosis of median rhomboid glossitis is essentially a clinical, the role of *Candida* can be proved by isolation of pathogenic *Candida* species from the lesion by laboratory techniques such as smear, culture of *Candida* on Sabouraud's dextrose agar, colony forming units and CHROM agar test.

The characteristic histopathological features have been studied by Sammet which include loss of papillae with varying degrees of parakeratosis, downward proliferation of spinous layer forming elongation of rete ridges which branch and anastomose, lymphocytic proliferation and presence of fungal hyphae readily seen by periodic acid Schiff (PAS) stain.^{3,7}

Conclusion

Median rhomboid glossitis was once thought to represent a developmental defect. Today, however, most authors do not subscribe to the embryogenesis theory. Instead, they believe that median rhomboid glossitis is related to an infection of *Candida albicans*. MRG still gives rise to questions concerning its importance and etiology. When MRG associate with kissing lesion immunosuppression should be suspected and it has been considered a marker of AIDS. So proper diagnosis and management of such lesions are essential.

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Recent Trends in Non-Surgical Periodontal Care for the General Dentist - A Review

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Abstract

The management of periodontal defects has been an ongoing challenge in clinical periodontics. In the recent past, attention has been focused more on regenerative and reconstructive therapies i.e. bone grafts, guided tissue regeneration, root conditioning, polypeptide growth factors, rather than on respective therapies. These therapeutic measures are shown to be limited in the predictability of healing and regenerative response in the modern clinical practice because oral environment presents several complicating factors that border regeneration. The 21st century appears to represent a time in history when there is a convergence between clinical dentistry and medicine, human genetics, developmental and molecular biology, biotechnology, bioengineering, and bioinformatics, resulting in the emergence of novel regenerative therapeutic approaches and focusing mainly on non surgical modalities.

The purpose of this article is to provide a review of the various non surgical therapies in use today. Future direction in this ever-changing field is also discussed. Techniques currently in use are reviewed and evaluated. They include Probiotics, Ozone therapy, Photodynamic therapy, Gene therapy, RNA interference, Nanotechnology, Perioprotect, TIPS & BOST.

Keywords: Periodontics, oral environment, non-surgical therapy, probiotics.

Introduction

Advances in periodontal science and practice over the last decade have radically changed the understanding of periodontal diseases and have opened new, exciting prospects for both non-surgical and surgical therapy of periodontal diseases. Mechanical methods of subgingival debridement accomplished by thorough

scaling and root planing, accompanied by oral hygiene procedures, have served as the gold standard of periodontal therapy for decades.

Current research is presently on-going to evaluate modified manual, ultrasonic, and sonic tip designs; combined treatments using ultrasonic/sonic with subgingival chemotherapeutics; and regenerative periodontal surgery, microsurgery, photodynamic therapy, tissue engineering.

Probiotics

The World Health Organization (WHO) has defined Probiotics as live organisms, which, when administered in adequate amounts, confer a health benefit on the host. Probiotics repopulate beneficial bacteria which can help to kill the pathogenic bacteria and fight against infection. They are also called “friendly bacteria” or “good bacteria”.¹ Probiotics (Gibson GR & Roberfroid MB, 1995)² is defined as “non-absorbable food components that beneficially stimulate one or more of the beneficial microbe groups and thus have a positive effect on human health”. Similarly, Synbiotics (Harish K & Varghese T, 2006)² has been defined as “combined administration of specific prebiotics with probiotics to provide definite health benefits by synergistic action”.

Probiotics can be bacteria, moulds, yeast. But most probiotics are bacteria. Among bacteria, lactic acid bacteria are more popular. Lactobacillus acidophilus, L. casei, L. lactis, L. salivarius, L. plantrum, L. bulgaricus,

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L. rhamnosus, *L. reuteri*, *Streptococcus thermophilus*, *E. faecalis*, *Bifidobacterium bifidum* are commonly used bacterial probiotics. Probiotics can be in powder form, liquid form, gel, paste, granules or available in the form of capsules, sachets, etc.³

The physiological effects attributed to Probiotic bacteria include⁴- (1) reduction of gut PH, (2) Production of antibacterial substances, e.g., organic acids, bacteriocins, hydrogen peroxide, diacetyl acetaldehyde, lactoperoxidase system, lactones, and other unidentified substances, (3) reconstruction of normal intestinal microflora after disorders caused by diarrhoea, antibiotic therapy, and radiotherapy,⁴ reduction of cholesterol level in the blood and stimulation of immune functions.

Probiotics and Periodontal Health

Probiotics lower the pH in the oral cavity so that Pathogenic bacteria cannot form dental plaque and calculus that causes the periodontal disease. They make an excellent maintenance product because they produce antioxidants. Antioxidants prevent plaque formation by neutralizing the free electrons that are needed for the mineral formation. Probiotics are able to breakdown putrescence odours by fixating on the toxic gases (volatile sulphur compounds) and changing them to gases needed for metabolism.

Lactobacilli can produce different antimicrobial components including organic acids, hydrogen peroxide, low molecular weight antimicrobial substances, bacteriocins and adhesion inhibitors and have gained prominence as Probiotics. A majority of the strains including *L.salivarius* were shown to suppress the growth of *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, *Porphyromonos gingivalis* and *Prevotella intermedia*. Probiotic strains included in periodontal dressings at optimal concentration of 10⁸ CFU/ml were shown to diminish the number of most frequently isolated periodontal pathogens.⁵

Ozone Therapy⁶

Ozone is a chemical compound consisting of three oxygen atoms O₃ (i.e. triatomic oxygen), a highly energetic form of normal (diatomic) atmospheric oxygen (O₂). Oxygen/ozone therapy has a long history of research and clinical application with humans. Due to its being an extremely powerful oxidizing agent and a highly effective disinfectant, it is used throughout the world to destroy germs in water treatment installations supplying drinking water.

The German chemist, C.D. Schonbein, first discovered ozone in 1840. The first medical application was in 1870 when Dr. C. Lender purified blood in test tubes. Medical applications thereafter became widespread throughout Europe and America. Today, more than 114 diseases were listed for treatment with oxygen/ ozone therapy. Interestingly enough, in 1930, a German dentist, Dr. E.A. Fisch, used ozone on a regular basis in his dental practice in Zurich, Switzerland, and published numerous papers on the subject. Dr. Fisch influenced the work of Dr. Erwin Payr, a renowned surgeon. Dr. Payr's work set the stage for mainstream use of oxygen/ozone therapy in medicine.

Ozone is a powerful oxidizer — it effectively kills bacteria, fungi, viruses, and parasites at a dramatically lower concentration than chlorine, with none of the toxic side effects. One molecule of ozone is equal to between 3,000 to 10,000 molecules of chlorine and it kills pathogenic organisms 3,500 times faster!

Application of Ozone Therapy

Three basic forms of application to oral tissue are applied —1) ozonated water, 2) ozonated olive oil, and 3) oxygen/ozone gas. The rationale behind use of ozone is the safety, efficacy and non- toxicity or side effects.

Ozone therapy

Effects	Medical Uses
Activation of red blood cell metabolism improved oxygen supply.	Arterial circulatory disorders (peripheral and cerebral in particular) add. Complementary in various kinds of cancer.
Activation of immune cells the body releases its own vital cytokines, such as interferon's and interleukins.	Revitalization. General immune weakness.
Increase and activation of the body's own antioxidants and radical scavengers	Inflammatory processes, e.g. arthritis, reactivated arthritis, vascular conditions; age related processes

Periodontal Vaccine⁷

The primary role of any periodontal vaccine would be to eradicate the global periodontal disease burden with the ultimate purpose of lowering periodontal disease associated morbidity in humans. As an innovative strategy, vaccines using cross-reactive immunodominant epitopes as antigenic molecules in an attempt to stimulate antigen-specific regulatory T-cells (Tregs, CD4+, CD25+, FoxP3+), secreting IL-10 and TGF-β, may provide new clues for periodontal disease prevention, through the induction of either immune tolerance or an effector function.

Periodontal disease as a multifactorial and polymicrobial disease requires a sophisticated vaccine design regimen targeting multiple pathogenic species. Vaccine regimens including the commonly shared antigens by selected periodontopathogenic species would be considered an innovative strategy.

Photodynamic Therapy⁸

Photodynamic therapy is based on the principle that a photoactivatable substance (the photosensitizer) binds to the target cell and can be activated by light of a suitable wavelength. During this process, free radicals are formed (among them singlet oxygen), which then produce an effect that is toxic to the cell.

Mechanism of Action

Briefly, upon illumination, the photosensitizer is excited from the ground state to the triplet state. The longer life time of the triplet state enables the interaction of the excited photosensitizer with the surrounding molecules, and it is generally accepted that the generation of the cytotoxic species takes place during PDT while in this state only. The cytotoxic product, usually O₂ cannot migrate >0.02mm after its formation, thus making it ideal for the local application of PDT without endangering distant molecules, cells, or organs.

Fig1: Mechanism of Action

Advantages

PDT is also beneficial during the maintenance of periodontal therapy because it may act on the biofilm and eliminate the need for the removal of additional root substance by mechanical retreatment. Thus, the patient may experience less dentinal hypersensitivity.

This therapy also serves as an adjunct to mechanical therapy in sites with difficult access.

Adverse effects

- PDT has the potential of phototoxic and photo-allergic unwanted side effects
- There may be impairment of benign oral flora which may lead to an overgrowth of a single resistant species
- Histologically scar formation is evident
- Has the potential of promoting genotoxic effects

Gene Therapy⁹

Application of growth factors or soluble forms of cytokine receptors by gene transfer provides a greater sustainability than that of single protein application. Gene therapy may achieve greater bioavailability of growth factors within periodontal wounds, which may provide greater regenerative potential.

Gene delivery methods

Genetic engineering approaches generally consist of two modalities: in vivo and ex vivo gene delivery. In the former, gene constructs, such as expression plasmid DNA or a viral particle, are physically entrapped within a scaffold or matrix. When the scaffold containing the gene constructs is implanted into the tissue defect, the host cells migrate into the implant, take up the gene constructs and start to produce the encoded protein.

In the latter approach, cultured cells are transfected (in Nonviral delivery systems) or transduced (in viral delivery systems) with gene constructs in vitro before they are transplanted into the tissue defect.

Figure 2. Gene delivery approaches for periodontal tissue engineering. (A) Ex vivo gene delivery. (B) The in vivo gene transfer

Gene Activated Matrix (GAM)

It has been produced based on the principle of combination of naked DNA with a biodegradable carrier.

Limitation

- Difficulties in the preparation of collagen based GAMs and the enormous amount of plasmid required may limit its clinical use.
- Gene therapy studies utilizing bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs) have also been performed and bone morphogenetic protein-7 (BMP-7) transduced fibroblasts were used to stimulate repair of alveolar bone wounds and represent the first successful evidence of periodontal tissue engineering employing *ex vivo* gene transfer of bone morphogenetic proteins.

Advantages

- Safer and more cost-effective than cell-based therapies.
- Mimic the complex natural process of periodontal tissue formation, because multiple genes, and multiple factors, can be delivered within the bone defect.

RNA Interference¹⁰

The RNA-mediated silencing process is defined as RNAi, a discovery for which Fire and Mello received the 2006 Nobel Prize.

RNAi works through small RNAs of approximately 20 to 30 nucleotides that guide the degradation of complementary or semi complementary molecules of messenger RNAs (posttranscriptional gene silencing) or interfere with the expression of certain genes at the promoter level (transcriptional gene silencing).

RNAi in periodontal regeneration

Through the silencing of genes that negatively control cell proliferation and cell differentiation or genes that induce inflammation or apoptosis, RNAi may favor tissue regeneration.

Tumor necrosis factor- α -targeted siRNA can suppress osteolysis induced by metal particles in a murine calvaria model, opening the way to the application of RNAi in orthopedic and dental implant therapy.

(a) Mechanism of the posttranscriptional RNA mediated gene silencing.

(b) Mechanism of artificially induced posttranscriptional gene silencing.

(c) Mechanism of Transcriptional gene silencing.

Nanotechnology¹¹

"The science and technology of diagnosing treating and preventing disease and traumatic injury of relieving pain, and of preserving and improving human health, through the use of nanoscale structured materials, biotechnology and genetic engineering and eventually complex molecular machine system and Nanorobots".

Nanorobotics in Dentistry

Nanorobots induce oral analgesia, Desensitize tooth, manipulate the tissue to re-align and straighten irregular set of teeth and to improve durability of teeth.

Nanotechnology in Periodontics**Mechanism of action**

Functions may be controlled by an onboard nanocomputer executing programmed instructions in response to local sensor stimuli. Alternatively, the dentist may issue strategic instructions by transmitting his orders directly to *in vivo* nanorobots via acoustic signals (e.g. ultrasound) or by other means.

Treatment Opportunities in Periodontics

- Tooth Repair
- Hypersensitivity Cure
- Nanorobotic Dentifrice (Dentifrobots)

Waterlase¹²

Erbium-Chromium doped: Yttrium-Selenium-Gallium-Garnet (Er, Cr: YSGG) laser is commercially available as Waterlase . It uses a patented combination of laser energy and water by a process called Hydro photonics, to perform a wide range of dental procedures.

Drawbacks

As the Waterlase is quite expensive, it may not make it into many smaller dental practices.

Perioprotect

PerioProtect is a comprehensive method that is customized for individual patients to help manage biofilms, growing in the spaces or pockets between teeth and gum tissue. The overall goal of the Perio Protect Method is to manage oral biofilm with minimally invasive dentistry for lasting oral health.

The Method is a combination of treatments, including a non-invasive chemical debriding therapy used in conjunction with traditional mechanical debriding procedures. The chemical therapy involves a tray delivery of doctor-prescribed solutions to chemically debride biofilm from the periodontal pocket and alter the pocket's microbiological environment to disrupt biofilm growth.

Tri-Immunophasic Therapy¹³

William Hoisington has developed a new technique for treatment that allegedly tackles the issue of periodontal disease in an entirely new way.

Development of TIP and BOST

TIP and BOST have been elaborated and tested over the past several years on over 2,500 patients with remarkably consistent success in saving teeth thought lost, and limiting anaerobic bacteria generated inflammation to an acceptable minimum (Hoisington et al 2005).

Technique

First DNA test should be done to identify the bacteria to choose the antibiotic of choice. Gingiva is intentionally stretched with the rounded back of currettes in a three stage process. The tissue becomes more stretched as the instruments advance down to the bone level.

Here the currettes are inverted to allow the rounded tip of the currettes to plasty the surface of the bone and remove any attached granulation tissue or degenerated attachment. The goal is a smooth, regular bone surface and fresh bleeding to flush out bacteria and toxins from the porosities. right, where the immune reaction of inflammation can change into one of regeneration. This type of healing happens with the help of the stem cells from the periodontal ligament. The clot that is firmly attached to the clean bone serves as a scaffold. The stem cells can move along it and up the root surfaces at the rate of 0.5mm per day for eight days and thicken the layer on the clot. To permit this activity it is also important to keep the epithelial attachment away from the roots. This is done with the oral hygiene technique that keeps the pocket open and also inhibits the reformation of the sticky layer.

As healing time increases, the pockets gradually fill in from the bottom with very dense, partially mineralised connective tissue in about four to six weeks, and finally will become acellular.

Conclusion

Clinicians should continue to develop and enhance their diagnostic skills, assess factors that affect diagnosis and prognosis, formulate a comprehensive treatment plan, render appropriate treatment, evaluate the outcome and determine when periodontal care is indicated.

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Endo - Perio Lesion – A Case Report

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Abstract

Bacterial infections play an important role in the vast majority of pulpal and periodontal lesions. Such infections usually account for more than 50% of the tooth mortality. Endo-perio lesions primarily occur by way of the intimate anatomic and vascular connection. Accurate diagnostic tests must be carried out to confirm pulp necrosis and careful diagnostic probing should be done to distinguish between endo-perio lesions.

Keywords: Periodontitis, perio-endo lesion, furcation.

Introduction

The Periodontium and endodontium develop with a shared root, which results in numerous communication channels, which may lead to the spread of pathological disorders.¹ The extension of disease from a periodontal pocket to the pulp are through patent dentinal tubules, lateral canals, and the apical foramen or foramina.² Alongside these anatomically predetermined paths, the formation of non-physiological connections like root perforations or vertical root fractures³ is also possible. The expression endo-perio lesion was devised to describe the etiopathogenesis in such cases and in lesions (i) Caused by endodontic pathogens that have spread coronally, thus involving the gingival margin and in some cases creating a fistula, or sinus tract, (ii) Originating from a marginal lesion which has subsequently affected more apical periodontal areas, (iii) Resulting from of a combination of the above, in which case the differential diagnosis must attribute each portion of the lesion to its cause.

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Case Report

A 38 years old female patient reported to Department of Periodontics with chief complain of dull pain in relation with lower right posterior region of the jaw since last one month. On intraoral examination with UNC-15 probe, it was observed that there was a pocket depth of 11 mm on buccal aspect of 46 was present with furcation involvement (Fig.01).

Fig.01. Probing depth 11mm

Fig.02. IOPA showing radiolucent area

No signs of mobility and tenderness on percussion were present. An intraoral Periapical radiograph of that region revealed a large radiolucent area at the apical aspect of 46 mimicking grade III furcation involvements (Fig.02). Also the tooth was found to be non vital when pulp vitality test was done. Henceforth, root canal treatment was done with 46 along with scaling and polishing.

The patient was recalled after three month, but no significant reduction in pocket depth was found. Under local anaesthesia sulcular incision was given and the flap was reflected (Fig.03). Granulation tissue was removed and root planing was done. On checking with Nabers probe, lingual cortical plate was found to be intact and it was a typical case of grade II furcation involvement revealing cul-de-sac (Fig.04). After thorough debridement, graft was placed (Perioglas) along with collagen membrane covering the defect (Periocol) (Fig.05). The flap was then sutured with interrupted sutures and periodontal dressing was given (Fig.06). Patient was recalled after 8 days and sutures were removed.

Fig.03. Flap reflection and debridement

Fig.04. Detection of furcation involvement with Nabers probe

Fig.05. Placement of bone graft

Fig.06. Periodontal Dressing collagen membrane

At the end of six months, there were no symptoms of any pain or discomfort. On examination the pocket was reduced from 11mm to 4mm (Fig.07) and radiograph showed bone formation in apical portion of the defect (Fig.08).

Fig.07. At 6 months postoperative

Fig.08. Bone fill in Radiograph

Discussion

It was a typical case of primary endodontic lesion with a secondary involvement of periodontal tissue. On flap reflection, it revealed a typical cul-de-sac feature leading to grade II furcation involvement. In combined periodontal-endodontic lesion, only part of the lesion heals to the level of the secondary periodontal lesion. In general, healing of the tissue damaged by suppuration from the pulp space can be anticipated. Primary endodontic lesions with secondary periodontal involvement may also occur as a result of root perforation during root canal treatment, or where pins or posts have been misplaced during coronal restoration.¹⁰ Unlike teeth with periodontal-related lesions, teeth with endodontic-related lesions mainly feature extensive restorations. In contrast to teeth with endodontal lesions, periodontal lesions are often visible in combination with local factors (plaque/calculus). Whereas periodontal-related lesions which generally involve increased exploratory depth, endodontal related lesions as in the case mentioned; during probing, at one particular aspect of the tooth, the probe ‘disappears’ into a deep, narrow, fistula-like defect.

Symptoms may be acute, with periodontal abscess formation associated with pain, swelling, pus or exudate, pocket formation, and tooth mobility. A more chronic response may sometimes occur without pain, and involves the sudden appearance of a pocket with bleeding on probing or exudation of pus. When the root perforation is situated close to the alveolar crest, it may be possible to raise a flap and repair the defect with an appropriate filling material. In deeper perforations, or in the roof of the fucation, immediate repair of the perforation has a better prognosis than management of an infected one. Use of mineral trioxide aggregate has resulted in cemental healing following immediate repair.⁴

The prognosis and treatment of each endodontic–periodontal disease varies. Primary endodontic disease should only be treated by endodontic therapy and has a good prognosis. Primary periodontal disease should only be treated by periodontal therapy. In this case, the prognosis depends on severity of the periodontal disease and patient response. Primary endodontic disease with secondary periodontal involvement should first be treated with endodontic therapy. Treatment results should be evaluated in 2–3 months and only then should periodontal treatment be considered. This sequence of treatment allows sufficient time for initial tissue healing and better assessment of the periodontal condition.^{5, 6} It also reduces the potential risk of introducing bacteria and their byproducts during the initial healing phase. In this regard, it was suggested that the periodontal healing was adversely affected by aggressive removal of the periodontal ligament and underlying cementum during interim endodontic therapy.⁷ Terminology currently used in literature adds to the confusion of accurate identification of various lesions resulting in defects that can be probed. Recently a new classification for periodontal diseases and conditions was adopted by the International Workshop for a Classification of Periodontal Diseases and Conditions and a category of ‘Periodontitis Associated With Endodontic Lesions’ and a subcategory of ‘combined periodontic–endodontic lesions’ was added to the classification.⁸ Combined lesions are defined as ‘those cases where there is any coalescence of endodontic and periodontal lesions.’⁹

It is estimated that 30–40% of all teeth have lateral or accessory canals and the majority of them are found in the apical third of the root.¹⁰

DeDeus¹¹⁻¹² found that 17% of teeth had lateral canals in the apical third of the root, about 9% in the middle third, and less than 2% in the coronal third. However, it seems that the prevalence of periodontal disease associated with lateral canals is relatively low.

Conclusion

The above case represents a typical primary endodontic-secondary periodontal involvement. Such lesions can be positively identified by careful probing and radiograph. Root canal treatment is the first treatment priority followed by periodontal therapy in treating perio-endo lesions.

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Intra oral periapical radiography – basics yet intrigue: A review

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Abstract

There had been a long standing requirement for dental students which would help them to understand the basic techniques for intraoral periapical radiographs. Intra oral periapical radiography is an adjunct to the clinical examination and provides useful information about the joint components. The periapical view shows the entire crown and root of the teeth which provides vital information to aid in the diagnosis of the most common dental diseases. This article highlights the basic principle, techniques, advantages and disadvantages of intraoral periapical radiography.

Key words: *Periapical radiographs, paralleling technique, bisecting technique.*

Introduction

Radiographic examinations are one of the primary diagnostic tools used in dentistry to determine disease states and formulate appropriate treatment.¹ Dr. Otto Walkhoff is credited with the first dental radiograph. Dental radiographs are valuable diagnostic tools when the image quality is adequate for proper interpretation² Dental radiography is consistently under-utilized in veterinary practice. In many procedures, diagnostic radiographs are essential for the production of a treatment plan and treatment may be contraindicated without them.³ Periapical radiographs (“peri” meaning “around” and apical meaning “apex” or end of tooth root) record images of the outlines, position and mesiodistal extent of the teeth and surrounding tissues.

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In periapical radiograph it is essential to obtain the full length of the tooth and at least 2 mm of the periapical bone.⁴ The purpose of the intraoral periapical examination is to obtain a view of the entire tooth and its surrounding structures.⁵ Intra oral Periapical radiography is a commonly used intraoral imaging technique in dental radiology and may be a component of intraoral periapical radiologic examination. Periapical radiographs provide important information about the teeth and surrounding bone. The film shows the entire crown and root of the teeth and surrounding alveolar bone which provides vital information to aid in the diagnosis of the most common dental diseases; specifically tooth decay, tooth abscesses and periodontal bone loss or gum disease. Additional important findings may be detected, including the condition of restorations, impacted teeth or broken tooth fragments and variations in tooth and bone anatomy.⁶

Need of Intraoral Periapical Radiographs

Periapical radiograph should show all of a tooth including surrounding bone.⁷ There are certain indications for the intra oral periapical radiography that includes:

Assessment of Periodontal Status:-

Intra oral periapical radiographs can be use for assessment of periodontal status for following significant features:

1. Receding bone height related to C.E.J.
2. Loss of bone at interproximal space or at furcation.
3. Widening of periodontal space.
4. Loss of integrity of lamina Dura.

Exodontia:-

1. For diagnosis and planning of treatment of fractured teeth.
2. For the distinction between complicated crown fracture (pulpally exposed) and uncomplicated crown fracture (not pulpally exposed).
3. Pre extraction planning for the developmental anomalies.
4. Assessment of root morphology, resorptive lesion and ankylosis.
5. Post extraction radiographs for root fragments and other co-lateral damages.

Conservative/Operative Procedures:-

1. Detection of the dental caries.
2. Intraoperative or post operative radiographs for the demonstration of file, position of gutta percha point in canal, and adequate filling of pulp canal.
3. Internal resorption, detection of developmental anomalies.
4. Detection of missing teeth, teeth with developmental anomalies E.g.:- dilacerations, supernumerary teeth, fusion etc.
5. Evaluation of implant postoperatively.^{3,8}

Technique for Periapical Radiography:-

Two exposure techniques are implemented for periapical radiography. Prior to presenting technique a clear understanding of the technique must be established, although the bisecting angle technique is utilized by the practitioners, the paralleling technique is the method of choice for intraoral radiography. The paralleling angle technique provides less image distortion and reduces excess radiation to the patient.^{5,9}

The Paralleling Technique:-

The paralleling technique is also known as “right angle technique” or “long cone technique”. It is used for both periapical and bitewing radiographs. In the case of periapical radiograph the film receptor should be placed parallel to the crown and root of the teeth being imaged and the central ray of the x-ray beam is directed at the right angle to the teeth and film. The orientation of the film, teeth and the central ray minimized the geometric distortion.^{1,7} (Fig.1)

Fig 1: Paralleling Technique: diagram of paralleling technique illustrating the relationship of the film and the teeth in the paralleling (right angle) technique.

The Paralleling principle, in essence, follows the five rules of accurate image formation to minimize the undesirable image characteristics of unsharpness, magnification and shape distortion. These rules are as follows:

1. The x-rays should originate from as small a focal spot as possible, that determined by manufacturer. Efforts should be made to minimize voluntary and involuntary motion unsharpness of film or x-ray tube. This will increase the size of the focal spot.
2. The distance between the focal spot and the object to be examined should always be as long as is practical.
3. The film should be as close as possible to the object being radiographed.
4. As far as is practical, the long axis of the object should be parallel to the film.
5. The central ray should be as nearly perpendicular to the film as possible to record the adjacent structures in their true spatial relationship.⁴

Instruments:-

The film holder consists of the 3 basic components:

1. A mechanism for holding the film packet parallel to the teeth that prevents the bending of the film.
2. A bite block or platform.
3. Beam Aiming Device:-This may or may not prevent the collimation of the beam.⁸

A number of commercial devices are available that will hold the film parallel and at varying distances from the teeth:

1. The XCP instruments (extension cone paralleling)
2. The precision rectangular collimating instruments which restrict the beam size at the patient's face to the size of radiograph.
3. The Stabe disposable film holder.
4. The snap- A-Ray intra oral film holder
5. A haemostat inserted through a flattened rubber bite block which will serve in much the same manner as the Snap-A- Ray film holder.¹⁰

The choice of holder is a matter of personal preference, RIN XCP holders as shown in the Fig.2.

Fig 2: Yellow colour coded posterior holder (RIN XCP), Blue colour coded anterior holder (RIN XCP), Red colour coded superbite posterior holder (for bitewing).

Technique:-

Select the appropriate holder and the film
 Maxillary and Mandibular Incisors & Canine
 The anterior holder should be used and the small film packet with its long axis vertical.
 Maxillary and Mandibular Premolar & Molar
 Posterior holder should be used (right or left) as per the case and large film packet (31x 41) mm with its long axis horizontal.

Key Points:-

1. Smooth white surface of the film must face towards the x-ray sources.
2. End of the film packet with imposed orientation dot should place opposite to the crown of the tooth.
3. Patient is positioned with head support with occlusal plane horizontal.

Placement of The Film In Patient's Mouth:-

For Maxillary Incisors & Canine:-

Placed the film sufficiently posterior to enabled it's height to be accommodate in palatal vault.

For Maxillary Premolar & Molar:-

Place the film in the middle of the palate to accommodate its height in palatal vault.

For Mandibular Incisor & Canine:-

Film is positioned in line with the lower canine or first premolar.

For Mandibular Premolar & Molars:-

Film is placed in lingual sulcus next to appropriate teeth.

The holder is rotated so that teeth to be imaged a touching the bite block placed the cotton wool roll on the reverse side of the bite block to keep the tooth & film parallel and make holder comfortable to stabilize holder. Ask the patient to bite gently. Locator ring is moved down the indicator rod until this just in contact with the patient face to obtain the correct focal spot to the film distance. Although the beam indicating device with locator ring this automatically both vertical and horizontal angles and centres the beam over the film. Exposure is made.⁸

Point of entry for different teeth used in paralleling technique is described in Table.1¹⁰

Table 1: Point of entry for different teeth used in paralleling technique

IMAGE FIELD	POINT OF ENTRY OF CENTRAL RAY
Maxillary central incisor	High on the lip, in midline just below the septum of nostril.
Maxillary lateral incisor	High on lip, about 1c.m. from midline.
Maxillary canine	Through the canine eminence at about the intersection of distal and inferior borders of ala of nose.
Maxillary Pre molar	Through the center of 2 nd premolar root, this point is usually below the pupil of the eye.
Maxillary Molar	Below the outer canthus of eye & the zygoma at position of maxillary second molar
Maxillary distal oblique molar projection	At maxillary 3 rd molar region, below the middle of zygomatic arch, distal to the lateral canthus of eye.
Mandibular centrolateral projection	Below the lower lip, about 1cm lateral to the midline
Mandibular canine	Nearly perpendicular to ala of the nose, over the position of canine, and about the 3cm above inferior border of mandible.
Mandibular pre molar	Below the pupil of eye, about 3cm above inferior border of mandible.
Mandibular molar projection	Below outer canthus of eye, about 3cm above inferior border of mandible.
Mandibular distal oblique molar projection	About 3cm above antigonal or inferior border of mandible in line with anterior border of ramus.

Advantages:-

1. Less magnification so geometrically accurate image can be produced.
2. The shadow of zygomatic process appears above apices of the molar teeth.
3. Good representation of periodontal bone level.
4. Minimal foreshortening or elongation gives accurate information about the periapical region of image of teeth.
5. Detection of a proximal caries because of well demonstration of crown of the teeth.
6. Automatically determine vertical and horizontal angulations by positioning device if placed correctly.
7. No coning of or cone cutting as the x-ray beam is aimed accurately ay the centre of the film.
8. Reproducible radiographs are possible relative postures of film & teeth and x ray been is always maintained in respective of patient's position.^{7,8}

Disadvantages:-

1. Positioning of the film can be uncomfortable for the posterior teeth.
2. Inexperienced operator can face difficulty in placing the holders in the mouth.
3. Cannot be performed satisfactory using short focal spot to skin distance.
4. Difficulty in placing the holder in lower third molar regions.
5. Holders used to be auto clave or disposable.
6. Cannot done in cases of shallow flat palate.
7. Sometimes apical region of the teeth may appear near the edge of the film.^{7,8}

Bisecting Angle Technique

Bisecting angle technique is used for periapical radiography it is a useful alternative technique when ideal receptor placement cannot be achieved due to patient's trauma or anatomical obstacles such as tori, shallow palate, and shallow floor of the mouth, short frenum, or narrow arch width. This technique is more operator sensitive. If angle is not correctly bisected elongation or foreshortening will occur.²

Principle:-

The bisecting angle technique is based on geometric principle that states that two triangles are equal if they have two equal angles and a common side, it is called "Scieszynsk's Rule of Isometry". Isometry is defined as equality of measurement when the rule of Isometry is applied to dental radiography. (Fig.3)

Fig 3: Rule of Isometry - Angle A is bisected by the line AC. Line AC is perpendicular to line BD. Angle DAC is equal to angle CAB, and angle ACD is equal to angle ACB. If two triangles have to equal angles a common side, then it can be said that the two triangles are equal. Therefore, triangle DAC is equal to triangle CAB.

It is used to determine correct vertical angulations of cone (B.I.D.). Bisecting angle rule states that the central ray is directed through the medial plane of tooth, perpendicular to a line bisecting the angle formed by the plane of long axis of tooth and plane of the film.^{4,7} (Fig.4)

Fig 4: Bisecting Angle Technique: The rule of isometry apply to the intraoral radiographic technique commonly called the bisection – of – the – angle technique. The path of central ray is directed perpendicular to a line bisecting the angles formed by the long axis of the tooth and the plane of the film.

Instruments Used:-

Many methods can be used to support the file for bisecting angle technique. The preferred method is to use a film holding instrument (SNAP-A-RAY) OR BISECTING TECHNIQUE INSTRUMENTS.

Two such film holders are the DENTSPLY/RINN BISECTING ANGLE INSTRUMENT (B.A.I.) film holders and the dentsply/rinn stable disposable periapical x-ray film holders.

Dentsply/Rinn (B.A.I.) Instruments:-

These instruments are designed to add in the determination of horizontal and vertical angulations, minimized distortion film bending and preventing cone-cutting.

Dentsply /Rinn Stab Film Holder’s:-

These film holders are made of exposed /rigid poly styrene material that allowing the patient’s teeth to penetrate the bite blocks portion and the film holder, locking it into position.

Technique:-

When using the bisecting angle technique the head position is very important, the rule for head position or patient’s positions as follows:-

1. The occlusal plane of teeth to be radiographed should be parallel to the floor.
2. Saggital plane should be perpendicular to the floor for maxillary Projection, here alatragus line is parallel to the floor.

3. In Mandibular projection, mandibular occlusal plane changes when mouth is opened, so patient’s head should be tilted slightly backward so that occlusal plane of the mandible will parallel to the floor when mouth open. Here lip commissural –tragus line is parallel to the floor.

Place the film to set the tooth to be imaged as close as possible. The angle formed between long axis of tooth and long axis of film assessed and mentally bisected. Place the x ray tube at right angle of the bisecting line with central ray aiming to the tooth apex. As per geometric principle of similar triangles, the length of tooth will be equal to length of the imaged tooth.^{4,7,8} Point of entry for different teeth used in Bisecting Angle technique is described in Table 2¹⁰

Table 2: Point of entry for different teeth used in bisecting technique

IMAGE FIELD	POINT OF ENTRY OF CENTRAL RAY
Maxillary central incisor	In midline, through tip of the nose.
Maxillary lateral incisor	Through ala of the nose, about 1cm from midline.
Maxillary canine	Through the canine eminence, through the ala of the nose.
Maxillary Pre molar	below the pupil of the eye, close to level of ala-tragus line
Maxillary Molar	On the cheek in line with outer canthus of eye, below the zygoma, and on anterioposterior level with 2 nd molar
Mandibular centrolateral incisor projection	Below the vermillion border of lip, about 1cm from the midline
Mandibular canine	Through the canine approx. 3cm from midline.
Mandibular pre molar	Below the pupil of eye approx 3cm above inferior border of mandible.
Mandibular molar	Below lateral canthus of eye approx. 3cm above inferior border of mandible.

Vertical Angulation

1. Rule for vertical angulations in bisecting angle technique is to direct the central ray through the centre of the filed under examination, perpendicular to the line bisecting the angle formed by the planes of long axis of the tooth and the plane of the film.
2. Plus (+) vertical angulations means cone is above the horizontal pointed downward.
3. Minus (-) vertical angulations means cone is below the horizontal pointed upward. The ranges of prescribed vertical angulations are listed in TABLE 3^{4,7}

Table 3: Ranges of prescribed vertical angulations for bisecting angle technique

PROJECTIONS	MAXILLA	MANDIBLE
Incisors	+ 40°	- 15°
Canines	+ 45°	-20°
Premolars	+ 30°	-10°
Molars	+ 20°	-5°

Horizontal Angulation

1. In the horizontal plane the central ray should be aimed through the inter proximal contact areas.
2. Horizontal angulations determined by shape of arch and position of tooth.

Periapical Radiography

Advantages:-

1. Placement of the film is simple and quick.
2. Positioning of the file is comfortable in all areas of the mouth.
3. The image tooth will be the same length as tooth itself and should be adequate for diagnostic purpose if all angulations are used correctly.

Disadvantages:-

1. Periodontal bone levels are shown poorly.
2. Non reproducible.
3. The shadow of zygomatic process overlies the root of maxillary molars.
4. Horizontal & vertical angles has to be assessed for every patient.
5. The technique required experienced operator.
6. An incorrect horizontal angulation causes overlapping of crown and root.
7. Incorrect vertical angulations will cause foreshortening or elongation of image.
8. Buccal roots of maxillary premolar and molar get foreshortened
9. Crown of teeth are often distorted thus preventing detection of proximal caries.
10. If central ray is not aimed at the centre of the film coning off or cone cut may result.^{7,8}

Conclusion

Diagnostic intra oral periapical radiography has evolved as an inseparable branch of dentistry. Intra oral periapical radiography is an important diagnostic aid and routinely used for investigating the periapical and periodontal diseases. Proper intra oral periapical technique not only helps to confirm the diagnosis but also aids treatment planning and management and baseline for assessing the outcome of each pulpal, periapical and periodontal pathologies.

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